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PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 25

Issue 1

Pages: 155-200

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2343

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13742211

Manuscript Accepted: 07-27-2024

Unveiling the Challenges of Teachers in the Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program

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Abstract

This study aimed to unveil the teachers' challenges in the implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program. It also looked into the similarities and differences among the participants in terms of challenges, copings and insights. This qualitative multiple case study explored the challenges, coping strategies and insights of six class advisers randomly selected for the study. Results revealed that based on the experiences of the participants, language barrier, limited parental involvement and lack of support and motivation from the administration were the challenges encountered in the implementation. But despite these challenges, some teachers managed to cope by becoming resourceful to reach out for support and collaboration with stakeholders and to persevere for the program. As for the insights gained by the participants, most of them emphasized the acceptance for positive change and for continuous improvement and embracing the holistic impact of the homeroom guidance program. This study may serve as a guide to researchers and educational leaders to have a deeper understanding about the challenging journey of teachers in shaping the course of future studies, fostering a continuous and informed discourse and proper monitoring on the evolving landscape of homeroom guidance in education for its effective implementation.

Keywords: *guidance and counseling, homeroom guidance program, challenges of teachers, copings, insights, implementation, philippines*

Introduction

Due to the outbreak of the Coronavirus, the Homeroom Guidance Program has become an alternative means for the Department of Education to cope with health and mental challenges. The Office of the Undersecretary for Curriculum and Instruction's DepEd Memorandum DM-OUCI-2021-346, dated August 25, 2021, which states the Revised Implementation of Homeroom Guidance (HG) During Crisis Situation for School Year 2021–2022 was the source of this change. The program aimed to promote proactive, preventive, and educative methods to support the learner's life skills development. However, implementing this program has proven challenging, especially when teachers, already fully loaded with academic subjects and other responsibilities, were expected to handle this ungraded subject (Llego, 2021).

Moreover, across East and Southeast Asia, school counseling needs present similarities, such as up-to-date, relevant training for school counselors and a specific school counseling model to guide the profession. The Taxonomy of Policy Levers to Promote High-Quality School-Based Counseling identifies specific levers to improve school counseling services. These levers suggest providing up-to-date training and regular supervision to school counselors, aligning school counseling policy with the school environment, and overcoming societal barriers like the stigma towards mental health. In Uganda, full-time classroom teachers who are also designated as counselors face significant challenges due to their lack of formal training in guidance and counseling. Similarly, in Malawi, school guidance and counseling are still in their infancy. Counselors need new tools and training as school counseling support grows to maintain successful and long-lasting practices (Larran & Hein, 2024; Knettel et al., 2019).

In Pangasinan, Philippines, increasing teacher awareness about Homeroom Guidance paves the way for acceptance and continued implementation. The work tenure results in familiarity with the job position and the ability to perform better on tasks, leading to increased efficiency and productivity. Proper time management and class scheduling reduce the difficulty teachers face in implementing Homeroom Guidance. Self-awareness assists managers in identifying situations where they will be most productive, making intuitive decisions, managing stress, and motivating themselves and others (Viray, 2022).

However, despite the growing emphasis on the importance of comprehensive guidance programs in schools, there is a significant knowledge gap concerning the specific challenges teachers face in implementing the Homeroom Guidance Program, particularly in the District of Malapatan 3. Existing literature primarily focuses on the benefits and outcomes of such programs, often overlooking the nuanced challenges that educators face in diverse contexts. There is limited research that explores the personal and professional coping mechanisms teachers use when facing these challenges. Furthermore, insights from teachers on how to improve the implementation process need to be documented, leaving a critical void in understanding how to support educators effectively. This study aimed to fill the gap by exploring teachers' real-world experiences and perspectives, contributing valuable insights to the academic and practical discourse on the Homeroom Guidance Program.

Conducting this research was urgent due to the escalating need for effective student support systems in schools, especially in light of the increasing mental health concerns among students exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic. Teachers play a vital role in successfully implementing the Homeroom Guidance Program, and their challenges directly impact the quality and efficacy of the program. Immediate insights into these challenges and coping strategies are essential to inform policymakers, educational leaders, and

training programs to enhance teacher support. Additionally, understanding the current state of the program's implementation in Malapatan 3 could provide timely recommendations for adjustments and improvements, ensuring that the program meets its intended goals of supporting student development and well-being.

Research Questions

This qualitative multiple-case study explored teachers' challenges in implementing the Homeroom Guidance Program. Specifically, it answered the following research questions:

1. How can the challenges teachers face in implementing the Homeroom Guidance program be described?
2. What are the similarities and differences among cases regarding challenges, copings, and insights?

Methodology

This section presents the research design, the role of the researcher, research participants, data collection, analysis of data, trustworthiness, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study utilized a qualitative research design. An expert state that qualitative research gathers information through open-ended and conversational communication. Furthermore, it entails collecting and analyzing non-numerical data such as text, video, or audio to comprehend concepts, opinions, or experiences. Qualitative research can be used to gain in-depth insights into a problem or generate new research ideas (Cristobal & De La Cruz-Cristobal, 2017).

Furthermore, a qualitative study is a research approach that helps investigate and interpret a central phenomenon. The researcher asked the participants a grand question to understand this phenomenon, collected participants' detailed views in words, pictures, or videos, and analyzed the information for explanations and themes. Additionally, the researcher discussed the significance of the knowledge from this information, drawing on personal reflections and previous studies (Flick, 2022).

Specifically, quantitative research aims to fully represent the diversity and depth of human experiences, viewpoints, attitudes, and actions. It aims to uncover insights that quantitative research might need to catch up on by going beyond fundamental statistical analysis. For qualitative research designs, data are usually gathered through focus groups, observations, interviews, and document or artifact analysis. Using these techniques, researchers can get comprehensive, illustrative data regarding participants' viewpoints, circumstances, and experiences (Jain, 2023).

In addition, multiple case study research is a qualitative methodology that allows researchers to contrast individual cases, represent a diversity of qualities and extremes to create depth, and understand a wide phenomenon without sacrificing the uniqueness of the specific case studies. A multiple-case study intentionally analyzes two or more complete single-case reports (Adams et al., 2022).

Multiple cases are selected so that individual case studies either predict similar results, a literal replication, or predict contrasting results but, for anticipatable reasons, a theoretical replication. When the study's goal is to compare and repeat the findings, the multiple-case study generates more convincing evidence, making it stronger than the single-case study (Alqahtani & Qu, 2019).

Several authors explained and justified the rationale of utilizing multiple-case design in qualitative research. Firstly, it explores a real-life multiple-bounded system through detailed, in-depth data gathering involving multiple sources of information. Secondly, using a multiple-case design to explore the research question and theoretical evolution will enable the researcher to understand the differences and similarities of information management of the WIL process between the three multiple cases studied. Finally, this enables the researcher to

address the complex issues that need to be explored in-depth and to understand the behavioral conditions of such a system based on the participants' comments, inputs, and interpretative perspectives. Using a multiple-case design, a comprehensive and in-depth description of the information management of WIL allows researchers to move beyond the quantitative statistical results of conventional research methodologies to understand the behavioral conditions through the perspectives of the respondents who are closely engaged in the information management of the WIL process (Brink, 2018).

Indeed, the multiple case study design is a valuable qualitative study tool in studying the links between the personal, social, behavioral, psychological, organizational, cultural, and environmental factors that guide organizational and leadership development. Case study research is necessary to examine participants' perceptions of the phenomenon in its natural setting (Halkias et al., 2022).

In this study, the researcher employed a qualitative multiple-case study design that involves two or more cases of the same phenomenon to get more varied evidence and cross-examination. A multiple case study was chosen since the researcher studied numerous cases to know the differences and similarities among the participants. As a result, the researcher could supply crucial influences on the literature based on its differences and similarities. Moreover, a multiple case study is needed to include more than one case. It is commonly associated with several experiments. Also, the number of cases depends on how much is known and how much new information the cases bring (Canlas & Mageswary, 2020).

The study was conducted in the two (2) schools of Malapatan 3 District, Lun Padidu National High School and Lun Padidu Central Elementary School. Six (6) class advisers handling Homeroom Guidance subjects were purposely selected for the study. With the participants' permission, an in-depth interview was conducted using a semi-structured interview guide and an audio recorder to gather data.

Participants

The study participants were the six (6) class advisers handling Homeroom Guidance subjects during the School Year 2022-2023. Three (3) class advisers hailed from Lun Padidu National High School, and another three (3) from Lun Padidu Central Elementary School. They were purposely selected for the study to discover the challenges that these teachers encounter in implementing the Homeroom Guidance Program in elementary and high school. The criteria for selection of participants of the study were the following: Teachers must be at least five (5) years and above in service, 40 years old and above in age, and a regular/permanent DepEd employee regardless of gender.

Data Collection

Experiments, observations, and the selection and collection of primary and secondary data were all crucial components of this research. Some primary data sources were case studies, interviews, surveys, and diary entries. Another common technique for gathering data is conducting interviews.

Requesting authorization from the organization is one of the researchers' primary duties. If the organization has a policy concerning research activities, the researcher needs to review it and decide how best to gain access to the subjects or data (Cyr et al., 2024). In this study, I first asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent, the District Supervisor, and then the School Principal for approval.

The study was conducted during the teacher-participants' free time, ensuring their classes was maintained.

The research's selection and collection of primary and secondary data are vital. Interviews are also a standard method of collecting data. Interviews can help the researcher learn how and why certain things happen to the people involved and their opinions, motivations, interests, and feelings. Thus, interviews are powerful when choosing the best research tool (Brett & Wheeler, 2021).

The actualization of the interview was presented face-to-face in an office, ensuring the confidentiality of the interview. Therefore, the interviewer and the interviewee could freely interact with one another.

Transcribing was the act of providing a written statement of the spoken responses of the study's participants. In qualitative research, the individual or group interviews are typically transcribed and written verbatim, and in qualitative research, they are precisely word-for-word (Hepburn & Bolden, 2017).

The researcher was responsible for ascertaining the suitable instrument for gathering data and the right one for transcribing the gathered information. The transcription process was highly labor-intensive and time-consuming. As a transcriber, I must make subjective choices regarding what to include and leave out, whether to gather errors and correct repetitive language (Nordstrom, 2020).

Protocols and transcripts must be made to assess the information obtained from focus groups, interviews, and observations. Interview transcripts can include behavioral annotations and phonetic transcriptions of dialects and filter words, depending on what is known to be relevant, vital, and expected for the research. Qualitative research papers are usually longer than quantitative ones to allow for "thick description" and in-depth understanding. A discussion of whether and how this may have influenced data collecting, analysis, and interpretation can take place thanks to the emphasis on transparency of the methods utilized, which includes why, how, and by whom the data is implemented in the particular study context (Busetto et al., 2020).

Data Analysis

When conducting a qualitative study, the researcher tried to get as close as possible to the participants being studied to minimize the distance between themselves and the participants. In order to convey the most important aspects of a research study, a large amount of data had to be summarized and presented. The methods used to evaluate the data include data reduction, data display,

conclusion, drawing, and verification. It was also noted that qualitative information might be used for qualitative content analysis, which looks for critical meanings and consistencies (Timmermans & Tavory, 2022).

In the first step, the researcher read a description of each person participating in the study to understand the participants. Next, the researcher extracts significant statements to the research question, describing their challenging experience as a Homeroom Guidance teacher. To analyze the significant statements, the researcher begins articulating what the statements mean and creates themes from the meanings. The researcher grouped similar themes and organizes them into categories. Finally, the researcher integrates the results into a comprehensive topic description and returns to each participant to verify the results (Hitchcock & Onwuegbuzie, 2022).

Discussions in a qualitative study needed to specify the steps in analyzing various forms of data. Analyzing text and various data types

is a complex undertaking for qualitative researchers. It also entails organizing the data, performing a preliminary database read-through, coding and grouping themes, displaying the data, and formulating an interpretation (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

Transcribing. While transcription was frequently regarded as a data collection component. It was also an analysis act. When the researcher manually transcribes an interview, for example, the researcher decides to convert the audio recording into text, shaping the researcher's analysis (Hennink et al., 2020).

The researcher's methodology and objectives influenced this choice and should be acknowledged as part of the researcher's analysis process. When the researcher works with participants to discuss sensitive topics, occurs in a cross-cultural environment, or the documentation must be translated into another language, planning and communicating the transcription process becomes even more challenging (Creswell & Báez, 2020).

Coding. Codes are labels that give symbolic meaning to descriptive or inferential data gathered during a study. They are typically assigned to data "chunks" or "units" of varying sizes and can take the form of a simple, descriptive label or a more evocative and complex label.

Categorizing. A category was formed by grouping codes related to one another due to their content or context. In other words, codes are classified as belonging to a category when they describe different aspects, similarities, or differences in the text's content.

When many codes resulted from the analysis, it was helpful to first assimilate smaller groups of closely related codes in sub-categories. Sub-categories related to one another by their content can then be grouped into categories. A category answered questions about who, what, when, and where. Categories, in other words, were an expression of manifest content or what is visible in the data. The category names are accurate and brief (Adu, 2019).

Formulating Themes. A theme was a patterned response derived from the data that informs the research question (Braun & Clarke, 2021).

A theme was a more abstract entity that required a greater degree of interpretation and data integration. As a researcher, I familiarized myself with the data I collected before analyzing individual items to formulate themes. It was vital to thoroughly understand the collected data (Humble & Radina, 2018).

Reporting. The final step was to write up the final analysis and description

of the findings. The writing process had already begun in some ways. Initial steps included taking notes, describing themes, and selecting representative data extracts. The final report went beyond describing codes and themes (Braun & Clarke, 2021).

In reporting, it was vital to organize all the ideas into a coherent narrative. The key to an organized report was its focus. The central idea or category must have strong explanatory power. The report has woven a narrative that explains how a researcher interprets the data and why his or her choice of themes and interpretation was made. The data were essential and correct.

The analysis described the data and provided context using both narrative descriptions and representative data extracts to argue why the researcher's explanation is rich and comprehensive in answering the research question. Any direct data extracts should include sufficient context to understand their meaning and be accompanied by an interwoven textual description that explains their significance (Jajuga et al., 2021).

Ethical Considerations

A primary critical consideration had distinct implications for this qualitative research. These issues and concerns came out basically from the methodology involved in this study. The ethical concerns applicable to this research were the study's appropriate operation, confidentiality, and anonymity. This study followed the standards of the Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges Ethics and Review Committee for the guidelines of ethical consideration, particularly in addressing the population and data such as, but not limited to:

Voluntary Participation. The participants were given the choice to participate without any expectation of consequences or loss of advantages. As a result, after the participants were informed of the study's goals and advantages, it became clear that their rights to contribute to the body of knowledge were carefully considered and anticipated. In this study, the participants were not forced to participate. They were permitted to withdraw their involvement if they felt uncomfortable during the study.

Privacy and Confidentiality. In compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which safeguards the fundamental human right to privacy, participants have the right to privacy, which may not be infringed upon without their informed consent. In this qualitative study, one approach to maintain privacy and secrecy was to address the participants' use of pseudonyms to hide their true identities. Moreover, concern over privacy and participant protections for humans was one barrier to data exchange. By protocol, the researcher was concerned with preserving the privacy and safety of research participants.

Informed Consent Process. The prospective research participants were to be fully informed about the research's objectives, methods, and benefits as comprehensively as possible within the framework of the study. The consent of the participants was obtained, indicating that their participation was asked for voluntarily. Thus, it was to be done in written form, stating all the essential details to be disclosed

to the participants and how the interview would be conducted. The participants were asked to affix their signature on the informed consent form confirming that they voluntarily agreed to participate in the survey. Since the participants were consenting adults, asking for parents' consent was unnecessary. The names of the information did not appear in any research instrument, and their answers are to be held confidential. The participants were aware that they may withdraw from the study at any time.

Furthermore, any data that I gathered was to be protected, and any information was released through a strict informed consent process. The participants had a sense of control over their personal information to lessen their fear that the data or information was to be used in any other unintended manner.

Recruitment. The participants were informed why they had become part of the study. To help the participants understand what the study was all about, I explained the purpose of the study so that they could infer from the researcher and view the essence of the study. Apart from the letter, I discussed the rationale of the study and its significance.

Risks. Research was conducted to determine if there was an acceptable positive benefit-risk ratio. In this study, the need to protect the participants from significant harm was equally important. The research effort prioritized the well-being of the participants. Furthermore, they were not harmed since their identity was confidential. Their protection and safety were the top priorities. As a researcher, I needed to ensure the participants were physically, emotionally, and socially ready. I ensured that the participants would not feel uncomfortable during the interview.

Benefits. This study was valuable to the participants since the results may act as an eye-opener for the DepEd authorities, school administrators, and all teachers to grasp the value of the Homeroom Guidance Program and the challenges encountered by the teachers in its implementation. Thus, it was conducted to unveil the teachers' experiences, learn their coping styles, and gain insights from them. Furthermore, to achieve more benefits in research, the researcher did all the aspects that would not harm the participants' lives and, thus, would benefit from further undertakings about the related studies. The rise of meaningful learning was the most essential part of achieving benefits.

Plagiarism. The study ensured no trace or evidence of misinterpretation of someone else's work. It was to be subjected to plagiarism detectors like Grammarly or Turnitin software. As a researcher, I felt a need to have positive character and integrity, which were associated with moral virtues and values. The researcher needed better knowledge about the paradigm of plagiarism to have a credible research paper.

Fabrication. The study had no indication or cue of purposive misinterpretation of what had been done. There must have been no making up of data and results or purposely putting forward conclusions that were not accurate. The researcher employed and integrated theories related to the information and other inferential concepts.

Authorship. I am currently enrolled in Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges Graduate School, General Santos City. I have undergone a series of revisions for my thesis based on the suggestions and recommendations made by my adviser, who guided me throughout the completion of this paper. The refinement of the paper was possible through the guidance of my adviser and the ERC committee.

Results

This section discusses the experiences of the interviewees and participants. Their stories, which were shared here, give us a good look at their challenges in guiding students in homeroom.

3.1. Participants

The research included six teachers selected randomly. Three served as class advisers at Lun Padidu National High School, while the other three were at Lun Padidu Central Elementary School. In securing their privacy, pseudonyms were assigned, and these fictional names were Venus, Star, Saturn, Milky Way, Mercury, and Earth.

Interviews were conducted in various locations based on the participants' preferences. I used a mobile phone as a recording device and used sheets of paper to jot down notes during the interviews, ensuring I captured all the essential observations. This approach guaranteed that no crucial insights from the participants were overlooked.

Participant 1: Venus

In this research, Venus, a dedicated 51-year-old Master Teacher-I, emerges as a valuable contributor, adding depth and richness to the study. Her unique combination of assertiveness and empathy makes her a fascinating subject. Hailing from Malapatan District, this Master Teacher-I exudes confidence in her professional role. Venus demonstrates leadership through decisive actions, supporting her teaching career with action research. She passionately explores and updates her teaching methods, integrating the latest trends to meet the diverse needs of her learners.

With an impressive 27 years of teaching in secondary education, Venus extends a motherly love and kindness that particularly resonates with learners facing challenges such as low socio-economic status, dysfunctional families, and special needs. Despite these hurdles, Venus dedicates herself to working compassionately and inspiring her learners. She consistently seeks strategies to maintain a balanced

lifestyle as a teacher, showcasing her commitment to professional growth and personal development. In the context of this case study, Venus emerges as a multifaceted and inspiring figure.

Moreover, Venus's willingness to share personal experiences and anecdotes enhances the qualitative aspect of the study, offering nuanced insights beyond mere theoretical understanding.

Participant 2: Star

My second participant aptly chose the name Star to represent her vibrant personality. At 43, she shines like one of the brilliant stars in our solar system. Although she has a humble demeanor, she harbors high aspirations to serve learners and reach prominent positions within the Department of Education.

With a commendable 19 years of teaching experience, Star is a competitive Master Teacher I in the Malapatan District. Her pursuit of post-graduate studies in her 30s has granted her an advantageous position in her current role. Star's journey has been marked by a willingness to learn from colleagues and mentors in DepEd, coupled with her exceptional listening skills, which have contributed to her current standing. Beyond her achievements, Star's proactive approach and eagerness to collaborate not only underscore her commitment to the study but also serve as an inspiration for others to engage in their educational pursuits actively.

Participant 3: Saturn

My next participant was Participant 3, affectionately known as Saturn. At 37 years old, Saturn holds the role of Teacher-III and brings a dedicated spirit to teaching both Mathematics and sports to her learners. Her candid feedback and responses to the researcher's interview questions have substantially contributed to the depth of this research.

Saturn's insights are characterized by a thoughtful and methodical approach, adding richness to discussions and guiding the exploration of complex themes within the research. With 12 years of teaching experience, her willingness to share personal experiences has significantly deepened her understanding of the subject matter, enhancing the qualitative aspects of my research. Through her considered reflections and articulate responses, Saturn plays an essential role in augmenting the comprehensiveness and richness of the research study, making a significant and invaluable contribution to the overarching goals of the investigation.

Participant 4: Milky Way

Participant 4 chose the colorful name Milky Way, reflecting her vibrant and vivacious personality. Milky Way is celebrated for her passion for teaching and remarkable leadership abilities, making her a valuable asset to the institution she serves. With an impressive tenure of nearly 30 years in the Department of Education, she brings much experience to the study.

Her diligence and articulate nature characterize the Milky Way. Her consistent ability to offer a unique perspective illuminates crucial facets of the subject matter. Through her articulate communication style and insightful observations, Milky Way acts as a catalyst, fostering engaging discussions that significantly enrich the overall quality of our case study. Her wealth of experience and expressive contributions make her a key figure in exploring the subject.

Participant 5: Mercury

The fifth participant was Mercury, a 49-year-old Master Teacher-I who embodies a remarkable blend of intellect and proactiveness in teaching and administrative roles. Despite juggling these responsibilities, she maintains a passion for Mathematics and demonstrates high discipline in organization, even though self-care may take a back seat due to her demanding schedule.

As a Master Teacher I, Mercury goes above and beyond her teaching duties, accomplishing multiple tasks with a commitment that reflects the trust placed in her by her superiors. Her zeal to serve and dedication to working harder than others have earned her the admiration and love of colleagues, supervisors, and school heads alike

Despite facing numerous challenges, Mercury's burning passion for molding her learners to the best of her ability shines through. Her story adds a compelling layer to the exploration of the realities and purpose of this study.

Participant 6: Earth

My last participant was aptly named Earth. She embodies qualities reminiscent of stability and nurturing guidance, both within her family and the broader educational ecosystem. At 59, this Teacher-III exudes humility and approachability, much like the Earth's diverse landscapes.

Similar to the Earth adapting to varied terrains, this educator tailors teaching methods to meet the unique needs of each student, creating an inclusive and supportive learning environment. With an impressive 34 years of teaching experience, Earthworks works tirelessly to support her students' growth, providing them with the tools and knowledge needed to flourish.

Much like the Earth sustains life, this educator's teaching style emphasizes interconnectedness, highlighting the impact of individual actions on the broader community. Through this approach, Earth instills in her students a sense of responsibility and empathy towards others and the world around them.

Earth, characterized as an educator with high regard for professional honesty, openly acknowledges some inconsistencies and challenges in delivering the learning process to her clients. This revelation sparked a more profound exploration by the researcher, driven by a desire to uncover more insights that could enhance the program under study.

3.2. Categorization of Data

The process of forming categories involved grouping codes that shared similarities in content or context. Codes are considered part of a category when they describe different aspects, similarities, or differences within the text's content.

When dealing with a large number of codes resulting from the analysis, it is beneficial to initially assimilate smaller groups of closely related codes into subcategories. Subcategories, connected by their content, can then be further

grouped into overarching categories. These categories answer questions about who, what, when, and where within the data, expressing the manifest content or what is visibly evident in the information (Kuckartz & Rädiker, 2023).

3.3. Analysis of Themes

For this part, I analyzed themes to dig deeper into each one. I not only looked at the main themes but also explored smaller sub-themes or subcategories, which gave me an excellent understanding of the whole picture. I backed up the findings with quotes from the interviews so that I could hear directly from the teachers.

As I went through each theme, I was not just telling you what was there but also figuring out what it all meant. I connected the dots between challenges and how teachers dealt with implementing Homeroom Guidance.

This theme analysis was not just about pointing out stuff; it was also about looking forward. I discussed what I have learned from teachers' experiences—its similarities and differences. In the end, I had made some suggestions based on what I found.

What is captivating about this part is that I was not just looking at one teacher at a time. I was comparing the experiences of different teachers, finding what was similar and what was different. This way, I got a complete picture of how teachers tackled the challenges of homeroom guidance, which gave a better understanding of all the different educational factors..

4. CASE 1-VENUS

Chapter 5 presented a detailed exploration of the experiences, challenges, and insights of Venus, a dedicated educator, in implementing the Homeroom Guidance Program. Venus shared valuable perspectives on her pedagogical approach, addressing difficulties, achievements, and the transformative impact on her students. This chapter probes her journey, revealing the tones of her teaching philosophy and the positive outcomes observed through the application of Homeroom Guidance.

Let me explore the various themes that have surfaced from the challenges Participant 1, Venus, encountered during the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program.

Language Barrier Challenges

The first emergent theme, "Language Barrier Challenges," explored the significant obstacle Venus faces in implementing the Homeroom Guidance program. Venus pointed out that students seek assistance due to the program being conducted in English. This challenge highlighted the linguistic barrier and underscored the need for effective communication in the learning process.

Venus's acknowledgment of this challenge prompted reflection on the broader implications for diverse learners. It raised questions about inclusivity and the adaptability of instructional materials to cater to students with varying language proficiencies. The theme emphasized recognizing and addressing language barriers to ensure equitable participation and understanding among all students.

In response to this emergent theme, strategies to mitigate language challenges include incorporating multilingual resources, providing language support, or fostering an inclusive learning environment that encourages students to express themselves comfortably in their preferred language. Exploring "Language Barrier Challenges" sheds light on creating an accessible and supportive educational atmosphere for all students, regardless of language background.

Students need assistance because the medium is English. So, they tried to ask me how to do the activity, and I observed that they also tried their best to comply with it (Lines 6-8).

Personal Qualities as Influential Variables

The second emergent theme, "Personal Qualities as Influential Variables," unveiled Venus's recognition of her personality's essential role in successfully implementing the Homeroom Guidance program. Venus acknowledges that her qualities, mainly being a mother and an earnest teacher, significantly influenced the learning environment. Her motherly love and dedication created a unique dynamic within the classroom, fostering a sense of trust and support among her students. This theme emphasized the profound impact of educators' personal qualities on the overall effectiveness of guidance programs, highlighting the importance of empathy, dedication, and mentorship in creating a positive and nurturing educational atmosphere.

Moreover, Venus's acknowledgment of her journey in integrating action research into her teaching pedagogy demonstrates a practical approach to professional development. Her willingness to explore and innovate aligns with the "Personal Qualities as Influential Variables" theme, emphasizing the transformative power of educators who actively engage in their growth. This theme encourages reflection on the personal qualities that educators bring to the classroom, highlighting the potential for positive change and inspiration when these qualities align with the goals of guidance programs.

So, one of the best or most essential variables is personality, and since I am a mother. It could improve teaching. I am just an ordinary teacher but serious about teaching. The personality matters most in the life of the students. The topic is personal or, shall we say, student-centered and in real-life situations. Most activities are in real-life situations. As teachers, we could also be models for them. Regarding challenges, let us share something about problems I have encountered and how to overcome the problems we encountered before (Lines 12-19).

Positive Attitude and Support for the Homeroom Guidance Program

The third emergent theme, "Positive Attitude and Support for Homeroom Guidance," captured Venus's enthusiastic endorsement of the program. Venus exuded a positive attitude toward the initiative, emphasizing its utility and significance in students' lives. Her laughter and affirming tone during the interview underscored her genuine support for the program, setting a positive tone within the classroom.

Venus's endorsement of the program extended beyond her perspective; she was a faithful advocate for its value. This theme suggested that fostering a positive attitude toward guidance programs can contribute to their success in implementation, the student's engagement, and the perception of the program's relevance. Venus's positive stance catalyzed student participation, creating an environment where learners are motivated to involve themselves in Homeroom Guidance activities actively.

This emergent theme prompted consideration of the broader educational context and the role of educators as advocates for initiatives that impact student well-being. It raised questions about the factors contributing to a positive attitude among educators and students regarding guidance programs, encouraging exploration of strategies to enhance overall program support and enthusiasm within educational communities.

As a teacher (laughing), I find Homeroom Guidance very useful and essential to the students because it is essential nowadays, aside from academics. Before ah ah, homeroom guidance was almost the same as GMRC, but I am proud and very supportive to the program of the government because that particular time intended for Homeroom Guidance, the time to talk to the students can share, share something about them, and they can also open their problems and based on the activities that they comply to be able to understand the learners who they are. I am proud of the Homeroom Guidance Program (Lines 23-31).

Empowering Students Through Homeroom Guidance Program

The fourth emergent theme, "Empowering Students through Homeroom Guidance," reflected Venus's commitment to equipping her students with the tools and mindset needed for personal and academic growth. Venus emphasized the program's role in encouraging students to be productive and proactive, instilling a sense of responsibility for their development. By encouraging learners to strive for continuous improvement rather than being content with their current achievements, Venus embodies a mentorship approach that goes beyond traditional teaching.

Venus's observation of her Grade 12 students, now actively engaging in their studies, indicates a tangible impact of the Homeroom Guidance program in empowering students. This theme prompted contemplation on the broader implications of educational initiatives in fostering a proactive and forward-thinking mindset among students. It invited educators to consider how guidance programs can be tailored to empower students, both academically and personally, nurturing a sense of agency and resilience that extends beyond the classroom.

Homeroom guidance is beneficial because it allows the students to share. So, based on the topics we have tackled, even this time, it's about the students' problems, what the problems they met are, and how to strategize on how to overcome them. Based on the Homeroom Guidance Program, we may get to know our students, and by doing so, we can strategize on how to attack or handle the problems they have encountered. It serves as a guide to our students (Lines 34-40).

In the following paragraphs, I have explored the five distinct themes that surfaced within the Coping Mechanisms category, shedding light on the participant's strategies and responses during the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance program.

Resource Provision and Limitations

The fifth emergent theme, "Resource Provision and Limitations," revolved around Venus's insights into the availability and constraints of resources during the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance program. Venus noted the variations in resource provision, highlighting the school's effort to provide hardcopy modules during the pandemic but facing limitations in the subsequent school year, where only softcopies were available to class advisers.

This theme emphasized the essential role of resources in effective program implementation and how limitations may impact educators' ability to facilitate meaningful learning experiences. It raised questions about the adaptability of teaching methods in the face of

resource constraints and the potential innovations required to overcome such challenges. Venus's observations underscored the importance of a supportive resource environment for educators, encouraging discussions on strategies to enhance resource accessibility and allocation for the successful execution of educational initiatives.

During the pandemic, the school provided materials such as hard copies of modules, but during the last School Year, the class advisers were also given soft copies (Lines 43-45).

Collective Implementation and Personal Innovations

The sixth emergent theme, "Collective Implementation and Personal Innovations," condensed Venus's observations on the collaborative efforts within her school community and her innovations in implementing the Homeroom Guidance program. Venus mentions the active participation of fellow teachers, particularly in the Science office, where they collectively printed copies for program activities. This collaborative approach shares the workload and fosters a sense of shared responsibility for program success.

Furthermore, Venus introduced her initiative of integrating reading into her Homeroom Guidance program. This personal innovation demonstrated Venus's commitment to tailoring the program to her students' specific needs and interests. This theme led to the consideration of the collective strength in implementing educational initiatives and the value of educators' innovations to enhance program effectiveness. It encouraged the exploration of collaborative strategies among educators within the school community while acknowledging the importance of personal adaptations to cater to the unique dynamics of each classroom.

Ahhhh, tactics. In our science office, We observed that teachers implement when they have time, so they attend their classes even though I attended the Homeroom Guidance class. We have noticed that the teachers print copies of the activities. It is difficult if the teachers will be the ones to finance the reproduction. Though it is not the modules, it takes three pages to print the materials. So, there are activities to print. We have noticed that our fellow teachers are implementing the Homeroom Guidance. We have yet to learn about other offices or departments (Lines 48-58a).

There are teachers who made mention na" *Uy RHGP ko ngayon. May klase ako*" (Lines 58b-59).

Some teachers mention, "Hey, it is my RHGP period. I have a class now.

So, about Academics in RHGP, I Also integrated reading (Lines 59-60b).

Collaborative Engagement with External Stakeholders

The seventh emergent theme, "Collaborative Engagement with External Stakeholders," unfolded as Venus discussed the Whole School Approach Program, emphasizing collaboration between the school, internal stakeholders, and external contributors, including parents. Venus highlighted the potential for external stakeholders, such as parents and graduates, to assist teachers in alleviating difficulties encountered during the Homeroom Guidance program's implementation.

This theme reflected the significance of community involvement in education and the potential benefits of external contributions to students' learning experiences. It encouraged educators to explore avenues for engaging external stakeholders and fostering partnerships beyond the classroom. Venus's experiences underscored the value of concerted efforts in enhancing the impact of educational initiatives, emphasizing the potential role of external stakeholders in enriching the learning environment and providing valuable insights and support to educators and students.

Since the school is the recipient of the Whole School Approach Program, it is not only the teachers who will implement it but who will implement it. It is a collaboration of the school, the internal and the e, its internal and even the parents. They, and can assist the teachers to lessen the difficulties encountered in the implementation of implementing ahh. With the external stakeholders, we can invite them to the classroom (Lines 64-69).

Halimbawa mga graduates we can invite them to speak, pwede silang gawing speaker sa classroom pwede for career guidance (Lines 69-71).

For instance, we can invite the graduates to speak; they can be speakers in the classroom to provide career guidance.

We practiced that before; We invited one of our then students into the class, so they inspired the students. Since this is Homeroom guidance, it will direct and provide career guidance to our learners on how they overcame their challenges through a talk show (Lines 71-75).

Engaging External Stakeholders for Inspiration

The eighth emergent theme, "Engaging External Stakeholders for Inspiration," surfaced as Venus shared her experience inviting a former learner at the Maritime Academy of Asia and the Pacific (MAAP) to speak to her students. In this theme, Venus highlighted the use of external inspiration to motivate her learners and broaden their perspectives on potential career paths.

This theme encouraged contemplation on the role of external stakeholders in providing real-world insights and acting as sources of inspiration for students. It highlighted the importance of exposing learners to diverse experiences and career possibilities, fostering a

sense of purpose and direction. Venus's positive approach in seeking external speakers exemplifies the potential for such engagements to positively impact students' aspirations and educational journeys, illustrating the theme's broader implications for creating enriching learning environments.

Parang external stakeholders. I have invited one of my learners who were in MAAP studying before, I showed them the video about the campus of MAAP and the offerings *para mainspire sila mag-aral doon* (Lines 78-80).

Like engaging external stakeholders, we invited one of the former learners studying at MAAP. We showed them a video showcasing the MAAP campus and its offerings to inspire them to consider studying there.

Resourceful Management of Limited Supplies

The ninth emergent theme, "Resourceful Management of Limited Supplies," displayed as Venus discussed coping with difficulties related to resource shortages, specifically the lack of supplies like bond papers. In response, Venus shared her innovative solution of utilizing used bond papers and printing activities on the back to optimize resources for classroom activities.

This theme invited reflection on educators' resourcefulness in overcoming constraints and finding practical solutions to challenges. It elicited considerations on how teachers can adapt and make the most of available resources to ensure continued effective program implementation. Venus's resourceful management served as a testament to educators' creativity and resilience in the face of limitations, inspiring conversations on strategies to support educators in maximizing the impact of their teaching initiatives within resource constraints.

So, difficulties. Lack of supply of resources like bondpapers, one of the techniques that I have used is the I used *mga* used bond papers *pwede yun printahan sa likod para magamit ng mga bata for activities. Ginagawa ko yun especially kapag marami akong bondpapers pero once a week lang naman. Pero sa mga non-readers kailangan talaga i-monitor ang mga bata if they are doing na activity* (Lines 82-87).

So, difficulties include the need for more resources like bond papers. One technique I have used is bond papers; they can be printed on the back so the children can use them for activities. We do this, especially when we have many bond papers, but it is only once a week. However, for non-readers, monitoring the children if they are doing the activity is necessary.

In the following paragraphs, we have explored various emergent themes within the Insights category, focusing on their relevance to implementing Homeroom Guidance.

Overcoming Challenges with a Motherly Approach

The tenth emergent theme, "Overcoming Challenges with a Motherly Approach," was unrolled as Venus shared her experiences handling two special students facing difficulties. Venus demonstrated a nurturing and compassionate stance and employed a motherly approach to guide her students through challenges and encourage their academic journey despite obstacles.

This theme caused reflection on the role of educators as not only instructors but also mentors and sources of support for students facing adversities. It highlighted the potential impact of a caring and empathetic approach in fostering resilience and determination among learners. Venus's motherly approach is an inspirational example, encouraging discussions on the importance of emotional support in education and strategies for educators to create a nurturing environment that enables students to overcome challenges.

Difficulties, so...this time it is the real scenario because I am handling two special students and how I overcame or how I overcome this problem(hehe) my students *silang dalawa mahirap man i- ano pero siyempre mahirap man i-level sa kanlia ang leksyon pero napaamo ko sila. Maybe siguro, I have shown to them my motherly approach bakit ang sabi ko dapat hindi kayo dito kasi ang isa sa kanila ay nagfailed sa First Quarter pero makita ko sa kanila na gusto pa rin silang mag-aral* (Lines 91-97).

Difficulties, so this time, it is a real scenario in handling two exceptional students and overcoming this problem. The two students may be challenging, but of course, it might not be easy to level the lesson for them, but I was able to pacify them. I showed them my motherly approach. I told them they should not be here because one failed in the first quarter, but seeing that they still wanted to study, teachers persuaded them.

Positive Changes and Continuous Improvement

The eleventh emergent theme, "Positive Changes and Continuous Improvement," took shape as Venus discussed the evolution of her experiences in implementing the Homeroom Guidance program. Venus observed positive changes in her students, noting a high pass rate and internalization of values related to career choices and personal development.

This theme encouraged contemplation on the transformative potential of educational initiatives and the importance of continuous improvement in pedagogical practices. It propelled consideration of how guidance programs can positively change students' attitudes and behaviors over time. Venus's insights invited discussions on the dynamic nature of teaching and the ongoing pursuit of improvement to enhance the effectiveness of educational interventions.

I have made mentioned that I am handling problematic learners but there are only a few who failed meaning *siguro nasa 90%*

naman ang pumasa. Maybe they have internalized also the value of choosing a career and dreaming to be a professional. Since it is a package ang Homeroom Guidance *kasali na doon* ang dreaming of what they wanted to become someday. Though *may mga flaws ba sa implementation ng program sa klase pero marami naman ang nareporma* (Lines 100-105).

I have mentioned that I am handling challenging learners, but only a few, meaning that around 90% passed. Maybe they have also internalized the value of choosing a career and dreaming of becoming a professional. The Homeroom Guidance package includes dreaming about what they want to become someday. Although there may be flaws in implementing the program in the class, many have been reformed.

Parental Role and Understanding

The twelfth emergent theme, "Parental Role and Understanding," unfolded as Venus emphasized the need for educators to act as both parents and models for students from broken families. She underscored the significance of understanding students' backgrounds and assuming a parental role to guide them effectively.

This theme prompted reflection on educators' multifaceted responsibilities and the impact of familial dynamics on students' educational journeys. It encouraged discussions on strategies for educators to play a supportive parental role in students' lives, fostering a sense of belonging and stability. Venus's insights lighten the importance of empathy and understanding in education, emphasizing educators' broader role in providing emotional support and guidance to students facing challenging family situations.

Ano siguro sa implementation kausapin sila at intindihin sila. Yun lang naman kasi many of our students are coming from broken families. They have no parents to guide them so as their teacher we need to act as parent in the school. Maybe I should serve as a parent and as a model to them. Ang mga kapit-bahay ko rito na mga students ko nakikita naman din nil ana maayos naman ang family ko (Lines 108-113).

Perhaps we should talk to them in the implementation, and we should talk underwater. That's because many of my students came from broken families. They have no parents to guide them, so as their teachers, we need to act as parents in the school. Maybe I should serve as a parent and as a role model to them. My neighbors here, who are my students, see that my family is doing well.

Dedication, Encouragement, and Growth

The fourteenth emergent theme, "Dedication, Encouragement, and Growth," emerged as Venus shared her commitment to teaching and the encouragement she imparts to her students. Venus stressed the importance of dedication in teaching, urging educators to approach their roles seriously. She emphasized that challenges are part of the journey and can contribute to students' growth, instilling a sense of resilience and determination.

This theme invited contemplation on the crucial role of educators' dedication and encouragement in fostering students' academic and personal growth. It prompted discussions on fostering a positive learning environment that values perseverance and continuous improvement. Venus's insights inspired conversations on strategies for educators to infuse dedication and encouragement into their teaching practices, contributing to student's holistic development.

Siguro yun ang ano ko lng na when regard to teaching, pinapakita ko talaga kung ano dapat si Ma'am magturo yung dedication sa teaching..we have to be serious in what you are doing . So, the simplest thing that you can do is you have to be serious kahit na sa bahay lang kayo as a working student pagbutihan nyo ang ginagawa nyo para tatagal kayo sa tinitirahan nyo. I always encourage my student to continue achieving their dreams. So, its normal to undergo challenges. Challenges will make them a better person in the future (Lines 116-122).

That may be what we believe when it comes to teaching. We show what a teacher should be—dedicated to teaching. We have to be serious about what we are doing. So, the simplest thing they can do is to be serious, even if they are just at home as a working student, and give their best in what to do, so that they will last in their residence. We always encourage the students to continue pursuing their dreams. So, it is customary to face challenges. Challenges will make them better individuals in the future.

Productivity, Future Building, and Benefits of the Homeroom Guidance Program

The fifteenth emergent theme, "Productivity, Future Building, and Benefits of Homeroom Guidance," materialized as Venus expressed the importance of teaching learners to be productive and proactive. She emphasized the value of the

Homeroom Guidance program in shaping students' perspectives toward building a future, stressing the program's role in providing career guidance and facilitating discussions about students' concerns.

This theme prompted reflection on the broader impact of guidance programs in promoting students' productivity, future planning, and overall well-being. It encourages discussions on the tangible benefits of Homeroom Guidance in equipping students with essential life skills and preparing them for future challenges. Venus's insights offered a fresh understanding of how such programs contribute to students' development, paving the way for conversations on optimizing the effectiveness of school guidance initiatives.

Many insights: Firstly, we teach our learners to be productive and proactive, not only for today, because, as I always tell them, we must

do our best; do not be contented with who we are today; build something new for the future. So, now, the first implementation, they are probably in Grade 12. So, when I see them, it is like they are active. They want to study, and the transformation of the children, we cannot generalize them because it also depends on how they were raised.

Table 1. *Thematic Analysis of Venus' Challenges, Coping Mechanisms, and Insights Learned in the Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program*

<i>Clustered Theme</i>	<i>Emergent Theme</i>
Challenges	
The medium of instruction was written in English Comprehension difficulty	Language Barrier Challenges
Copings	
During the pandemic, the school provided materials. Only the softcopy was given to the class advisers. Assist them in overcoming these obstacles	Overcoming Limitations and Resource Provision
Fellow teachers are implementing. Teachers are the ones who print copies for the activities. Integrated reading also.	Collective Implementation and Personal Innovations
The Whole School Approach is a collaboration. External stakeholders can assist the teachers. Provide career guidance to our learners.	Collaborative Engagement with External Stakeholders
External stakeholders Showed them the video about the campus Inspire them to study there	Engaging External Stakeholders for Inspiration
Lacking supply of resources like bond papers Used bond papers	Resource Management of Limited Supplies
Monitors the non-readers closely	
Insights	
Handling two special students Showed them the motherly approach Wanted to continue learning despite challenges	Overcoming Challenges with a Motherly Approach
Handling problematic learners About 90% have passed Many have been reformed	Positive Changes and Continuous Improvement
Talk to them and understand them. Many students are coming from broken families Serve as a parent and as a model	Parental Role and Understanding
Dedication in teaching Please encourage students to continue achieving their dreams Challenges will make them a better person	Dedication, Encouragement, and Growth
Teach learners to be productive and proactive Build something new for the future Homeroom Guidance is beneficial	Productivity, Future Building, and Benefits of Homeroom Guidance
Homeroom Guidance is very useful and essential to the students. I am pro and very supportive of the government program. I was able to understand the learners and who they are.	Positive Attitude and Support for Homeroom Guidance
Homeroom Guidance is beneficial because students can share. Strategize on how to overcome their problem Serves as a guide to our students	Empowering Students through Homeroom Guidance
Personality and being a mother. Just an ordinary teacher, but serious when it comes to teaching. Be a model to them	Personal Qualities as Influential Variables

5. CASE 2 - STAR

In Chapter 6, I explored the case of Star by examining her experiences and insights. Star, a competitive Master Teacher-1 in Malapatan District, brought a unique perspective to implementing the Homeroom Guidance program. With 19 years of teaching experience and a proactive approach to collaboration, Star's narrative unveils her challenges, coping mechanisms, and valuable insights gained throughout her journey. As I studied Star's experiences, I aimed to glean valuable lessons and discern emergent themes that contribute to the broader understanding of the complexities surrounding Homeroom Guidance in the educational scenario.

I have explored the various themes that surfaced while analyzing challenges in Star's implementation of Homeroom Guidance.

Persistent Absenteeism Impact

In Star's challenges, the emergent theme of "Persistent Absenteeism Impact" highlighted the significant impact of students' consistent

absence on the effectiveness of the Homeroom Guidance program. Star emphasized the challenge of being unable to give her full attention to the learners due to their frequent absenteeism. This persistent absenteeism posed a hurdle in fostering a consistent and meaningful connection with the students, hindering the program's intended impact. The theme sheds light on regular attendance's vital role in successfully implementing Homeroom Guidance, emphasizing the need for strategies to address and mitigate the consequences of persistent absenteeism for a more fruitful engagement with the program's objectives.

Maraming insights una parang we teach our learners to be productive and proactive sila not only for today because as I always tell them, but you also have to do your best, do not be contented on who you are today, build something new for the future. So, ngayon yung first implementation nasa Grade 12 na yata sila ngayon. So, kapag nakikita ko sila ayun parang active naman sila. Gusto sila mag-aral and ang transformation ng mga bata hindi naman natin ma-generalized ang mga bata depende na rin paano sila pinalaki basta as a teacher ok sa akin ang Homeroom Guidance dahil napag-uusapan talaga ang concerns ng mga bata. (Lines 124-132).

The main challenges that I have encountered in the classroom with the students are, um, they are consistent with their consistent absenteeism and full attention sometimes because they are frequently absent. If the parents are not supportive, then the learners in the classroom are, um, distant from school. There are issues in their homes. Sometimes, they are, um, not interested in going to school.

Material Dependency

In the realm of Star's challenges, the emergent theme of "Material Dependency" brought attention to the pivotal role that the availability of materials plays in facilitating the inclusion of Homeroom Guidance activities into regular classroom routines. Star highlighted the significance of having materials, expressing that the mere availability of reading materials provides her with a tangible resource to guide her program implementation. This theme underscored the dependence on essential materials for effective program execution. It emphasized the need for consistent access to resources to integrate Homeroom Guidance activities into the daily classroom routine seamlessly. Recognizing material dependency points to a critical aspect that educators like Star must address to enhance the program's accessibility and impact.

The materials are available because I have something to read and follow (Lines 148-149).

Positive Transformation and Heart-Centered Education

Within Star's challenges, the emergent theme of "Positive Transformation and Heart-Centered Education" signified her belief in the transformative power of Homeroom Guidance. Star expressed a positive attitude toward the program, seeing it as a catalyst for positive changes in learners' lives. This theme compressed the idea that Homeroom Guidance goes beyond academic instruction, aiming to nurture the hearts and minds of students. Star stressed the importance of embracing a heart-centered approach to education, emphasizing educators' role in shaping intellectual growth and fostering positive transformation in students' character and outlook on life. This theme reflected a commitment to holistic education and echoed the belief that Homeroom Guidance can be a catalyst for profound, positive changes in the lives of learners.

I am very optimistic about the program because it can transform our learners and their lives. It can improve them in many aspects and ways. We know the heart of education is educating the heart. That is why we need to implement a program that focuses on their attention and gives them the understanding that they are loved and essential (Lines 3-158).

Teachers as Second Parents and Continuous Support

In the context of Star's challenges, the emergent theme of "Teachers as Second Parents and Continuous Support" emphasized teachers' crucial role in students' lives, parallel to second parents. Star highlighted the challenges posed by students from broken families or facing various hardships. This theme underscored the significance of educators not only as academic guides but also as sources of emotional and moral support for students experiencing difficulties. The idea of teachers serving as second parents suggests a nurturing and supportive role wherein educators provide continuous support to help students overcome challenges and difficulties. This theme reinforced the notion that teachers, through their caring and supportive roles, contribute significantly to their students' overall well-being and development beyond the academic realm.

Yeah, Homeroom Guidance is beneficial. As second parents, we understand the learners' problems, feelings, problems, and personalities because we experience their personalities eight hours a day to learn their weaknesses and strengths. If we continue to implement it, we will be able to learn more about our learners and help them address their problems in life (Lines 161-166).

The following themes have been formulated based on Star's accounts of the coping mechanisms she employed.

External Support and Collaboration

The theme "External Support and Collaboration" emanated from Star's acknowledgment of the importance of support from external entities such as the Barangay Captains, Kagawads, and school administrators. Her recognition of the role these external stakeholders play in contributing to the success of the Homeroom Guidance program highlights the significance of partnership beyond the confines

of the classroom. This theme highlighted the interconnectedness of various elements within the community and administration that could impact the effectiveness of HRG implementation.

Last year, during the time of our previous principal, we knew we had a best friend who had helped and advised us. Because she is a guidance counselor, we knew if I had questions to ask, she could answer them because someone helped me. We invited our guidance counselor to be a speaker in our classroom (Lines 169-173).

Knowledge Sharing and Continuous Learning

The theme "Knowledge Sharing and Continuous

Learning" is derived from Star's acknowledgment of the value of learning from her co-teachers and the guidance counselor. Her openness to adopting tactics and innovations from more experienced colleagues reflects a commitment to ongoing learning. This theme emphasized the importance of collaborative knowledge-sharing among educators to implement the Homeroom Guidance program successfully. It underscored that continuous learning and exchanging insights contribute to more effective teaching strategies and coping mechanisms.

I have also tried some tactics from the co-teachers and our guidance counselor. It is very beneficial, especially since they are older. They have much experience in the past. We have also applied what we learned from them in the classroom. We also need to learn from them (Lines 176-179).

External Support and Impactful Regulations

Star highlighted the significance of external support, particularly from the Barangay Captains, Kagawads, and the school administration. She emphasized that their support could contribute significantly to the success of the Homeroom Guidance (HRG) program. Star mentioned the importance of cooperation in minimizing student distractions during school hours, such as restricting access to computer shops. She recognized the positive impact that supportive administrative rules and community dynamics could have on the practical implementation of HRG.

In essence, the emergent theme "External Support and Impactful Regulations" stressed the crucial role that external stakeholders and administrative regulations play in creating an environment conducive to successful HRG implementation. It reflected the idea that collaborative efforts with the community and supportive regulations can enhance the overall effectiveness of the HRG program.

Yeah, think if they can contribute a lot to the HRG, especially the support of the barangay captains and Kagawads.. if they are going to support the school with the ano ahhh, the learners like, for example, they will not allow the learners to play games during classes hours or school days just like the computer shops if they do not allow our learners to get inside the establishments, believe that this would be a great help for us. Also, the admin's support, like our bosses, will be beneficial (Lines 183-189).

Holistic Approach and Empathy

Star acknowledged her students' challenges, particularly those from broken families and experiencing various hardships. She emphasized the importance of adopting a holistic approach and showing empathy in dealing with learners who lack love and support from their parents. According to her, understanding and loving these students are crucial steps in positively impacting their lives. Star suggested that educators should refrain from being harsh and instead strive to comprehend their learners' diverse backgrounds and experiences.

In particular, the emergent theme of "Holistic Approach and Empathy" stressed the significance of embracing a comprehensive perspective in education. It emphasized the need for educators to go beyond academic instruction and consider the overall well-being of their students. Star's insights highlighted the transformative power of empathy and understanding in creating a supportive and nurturing learning environment.

We should not be harsh to our learners because some come from broken families and lack love from their parents; they have many misfortunes in their paths and experiences and experience much pain. That is why we must understand and learn to love them more. They can melt the heart of stone if they love and care for them. We need to talk to the parents. We also need to have seminars for the parents, and we also need to understand our learners. We must visit the at-home to understand our learners (Lines 192-200).

Positive Adaptation and Collaborative Learning

Star demonstrated a positive attitude and adaptive mindset when dealing with challenges. Despite facing difficulties, she expressed her commitment to thinking positively and adjusting her approach to accommodate the unique needs of her learners. Furthermore, she highlighted the importance of collaborative learning and knowledge-sharing among educators. Star shared that she learned valuable tactics from her co-teachers and the school's guidance counselor, emphasizing the benefits of collaborative efforts in overcoming obstacles.

The emergent theme "Positive Adaptation and Collaborative Learning" emphasized maintaining a positive outlook and adaptability

when facing challenges. Star's experiences highlighted the effectiveness of collaboration and the exchange of insights among educators to enhance the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance program. This theme emphasized the role of a constructive mindset and collaborative efforts in fostering a conducive learning environment.

Think positively, even if it is complex for learners to handle. Sometimes, it is really difficult to understand our learners because they come from different upbringings. Sometimes, we need to adjust our way of thinking, research, and ask fellow teachers and friends' guidance counselors (Lines 202-206).

The succeeding paragraphs and their respective themes have surfaced from the insights gleaned from Star's experiences

Balancing Act in Implementation

Star's experience underscored the delicate balance required in implementing the Homeroom Guidance program while managing a heavy workload. The theme "Balancing Act in Implementation" captured her challenges in allocating sufficient time and attention to HRG topics amidst a demanding schedule. This theme reflected the intricate juggling act teachers often perform to integrate valuable guidance elements into their teaching responsibilities.

When the HRG was implemented, I was so overloaded with subjects that I needed to focus on some..... topics in the HRG because I did not have that much time for them. We implemented it, but not entirely because we did not have time to give full attention, as we were overloaded with subjects last SY. We give time even if it is hard to budget the time (Lines 210-214).

HRG as a Facilitator

The theme of "HRG as a Facilitator" accentuated the essential role of the Homeroom Guidance (HRG) program in facilitating positive transformation and holistic development among students. Star emphasized the program's importance in influencing learners academically and in shaping their character and conduct. The notion of HRG as a facilitator aligns with Star's belief in heart-centered education, emphasizing the program's potential to fill students with valuable ideas, fostering a positive and transformative impact on their lives. This theme accentuated the broader scope of HRG beyond conventional academic aspects, positioning it as a catalyst for comprehensive student growth and self-discovery.

The HRG was very helpful to us teachers. It enabled us to handle things easily in the classroom, making the task of educating them easier (Lines 221-223).

Enhanced Teaching Philosophy

The emergent theme of "Enhanced Teaching Philosophy" captured Star's acknowledgment of the transformative impact that her involvement in the Homeroom Guidance (HRG) program has had on her pedagogical views. Through her experiences, she expressed a significant improvement in her teaching philosophy, particularly in recognizing the importance of focusing on her students' spiritual aspects and hearts. This theme highlighted how the HRG program has played a vital role in reshaping Star's approach to education, emphasizing a more holistic and heart-centered perspective in her teaching philosophy. It reflected the program's capacity not only to influence student growth but also to bring about a profound shift in the mindset and beliefs of educators, promoting a more encompassing and empathetic approach to teaching.

The way I think has improved the Philosophy of teaching. It would benefit the learners if we focused on the spiritual aspects and their hearts. (Lines 226-228)

Transformative Role of Homeroom Guidance

The emergent theme of the "Transformative Role of Homeroom Guidance" elucidated Star's recognition of the HRG program's pivotal role in effecting positive changes in educators and learners. Star emphasized how the program contributes to making classroom tasks more manageable and aids teachers in handling various challenges. This theme highlighted the transformative potential of HRG not only in students' lives but also in shaping the attitudes and approaches of teachers. It underscored the program's broader impact, illustrating how it has become an integral part of the educational ecosystem, fostering positive transformations in teaching and learning processes.

Homeroom Guidance is necessary for us to change our learners' ways of thinking because I believe in the theory of tabula rasa, which states that we are the ones who give them ideas so that they will be filled with ideas (Lines 231-233).

Holistic Impact of Homeroom Guidance

The theme "Holistic Impact of Homeroom Guidance" highlighted Star's recognition of the program's comprehensive influence on students. Star stressed the importance of HRG in academic aspects and in nurturing learners' hearts and conduct. She acknowledged the program's role in bringing about positive transformations beyond the curriculum, emphasizing character development and self-awareness. This theme captured the holistic impact of HRG, portraying it as a catalyst for positive change in various facets of students' lives. It emphasized the program's capacity to shape well-rounded individuals by addressing academic needs and their development's emotional and ethical dimensions.

All of the programs are important because they can change the lives of our learners. This program focuses not only on the curriculum but also on their conduct. It will enable our learners to better know themselves (Lines 235-238).

Table 2. *The Thematic Analysis of Star’s Challenges, Copings, and Insights Learned in the Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program*

<i>Clustered Theme Challenges</i>	<i>Emergent Theme</i>
Consistent student absenteeism Limited attention due to frequent absences Lack of parental support affecting learner engagement Material unavailability as a critical variable Dependence on reading and following provided materials. Impact of resource inaccessibility on Homeroom Guidance integration Overloaded with subjects Struggling to allocate time	Persistent Absenteeism Impact Material Dependency Teaching Load Balance
<i>Copings</i>	
Support from a trusted friend and guidance counselor Access to valuable advice and assistance Collaboration with the guidance counselor as a speaker in the classroom Learning from co-teachers and guidance counselor The benefit of tactics and innovations shared by experienced colleagues Application of acquired knowledge in the classroom Impact of External Variables on Homeroom Guidance Importance of support from barangay captains and kagawads Recognition of administrative support for effective implementation Empathy towards learners from broken families Importance of love and understanding in teaching Advocacy for parental involvement and seminars for parents Positive thinking as a coping mechanism Adaptation to diverse learner backgrounds Seeking advice from colleagues and guidance counselor Strong belief in the benefits of Homeroom Guidance Recognition of teachers as second parents understanding learners' problems Emphasis on continuous implementation for deeper understanding and support Highly positive attitude toward the Homeroom Guidance Program Belief in the program's transformative impact on learners Emphasis on the program as a means to educate the heart Commitment to partial implementation	External Support and Collaboration Knowledge Sharing and Continuous Learning External Support and Impactful Regulations Holistic Approach and Empathy Positive Adaptation and Collaborative Learning Teachers as Second Parents and Continuous Support Positive Transformation and Heart-Centered Education Balancing Act in Implementation
<i>Insights</i>	
HRG is a valuable aid Facilitating tasks in the classroom Easier education through HRG Improved teaching philosophy Focus on spiritual aspects Beneficial impact on learners Necessity of Homeroom Guidance Influence on learners' thinking Application of the theory of tabula rasa Importance of all programs Life-changing impact Self-awareness through the program	HRG as a Facilitator: Enhanced Teaching Philosophy Transformative Role of Homeroom Guidance Holistic Impact of Homeroom Guidance

6. CASE 3 - SATURN

Chapter 7 explored the experiences, challenges, and insights of Participant 3, referred to as Saturn. Through in-depth interviews, Saturn shared valuable perspectives on implementing the Homeroom Guidance program. This chapter explored the unique circumstances, coping strategies, and transformative insights that Saturn has gained throughout her journey. As unveiled by Saturn's narrative, the researcher aimed to illuminate the surfaced themes, shedding light on the complex dynamics of implementing Homeroom Guidance in a real-world classroom setting.

In the upcoming paragraphs, explore the themes that surfaced in Saturn's challenges while implementing the Homeroom Guidance program.

Struggling Balance

Saturn's experiences highlighted the inherent struggle to find an equilibrium between the demands of reproducing Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) for the Homeroom Guidance program and the overwhelming activities during face-to-face classes. This theme underscored the challenges educators face in managing various program components, impacting the comprehensive implementation of Homeroom Guidance within the given constraints.

One is the reproduction of SLM. Some of the learners were not able to answer the given activities in the module. But during face-to-face classes ahhh. The main challenge was I was not able to finish the modules of the Homeroom Guidance because of too many activities we have in school. *Na-implement lang siya pero not all.* Every module is very easy to answer because some topics are very relatable to learners (Lines 242-247).

One is the reproduction of SLM (Self-Learning Module). Some of the learners were unable to respond to the given activities in the module. However, during face-to-face classes, the main challenge was that we needed help to complete all the modules of the Homeroom Guidance due to the numerous activities we have in school. It was implemented, but not all modules were covered. Every module is straightforward to answer because some topics are highly relatable to learners.

Limited Schedule

Balancing Homeroom Guidance within Limited Schedule Saturn underscored the significant impact of the allocated schedule on the implementation of Homeroom Guidance, emphasizing the need for strategic selection of topics to maximize the limited time available. This theme revolved around the critical balance between time constraints and the commitment to adhering to the school's program, revealing the challenges of integrating the Homeroom Guidance activities into the regular classroom routine.

The most important variable is the schedule allotted for Homeroom Guidance. One hour every week. We select the most interesting topic. *Ibig sabihin not all topics. Pero because I abide by the school program* (Lines 251-253).

The most important variable is the schedule allocated for Homeroom Guidance: one hour every week. We select the most interesting topic—not all topics—because I abide by the school program.

Positive Perception, Time Limitations, and Selective Focus

Saturn's positive perception of the Homeroom Guidance program, recognizing its helpfulness, was compared with the challenge of time constraints. This theme revolved around the educator's willingness to confront challenges, highlighting the balance between a positive attitude and the practicality of addressing time limitations by selectively focusing on specific topics.

Actually, ok po ang Homeroom Guidance. Most of the topic are relatable to the learners in their day-to-day activity. Helpful siya sa students kaya lang limited lang ang iyang time unlike sa other subjects. Since once-a-week lang siya gusto ko pa sana i-discuss kaso lng kulang ang time. Kaya ang tendency selected topics lang ang tinuturo ko (Lines 257-261).

The Homeroom Guidance is okay. Most of the topics are relatable to the learners in their day-to-day activities. It's helpful to the students, but unlike in other subjects, its time is limited. Since it is only once a week, I would like to discuss more, but there needs to be more time. So, the tendency is to teach selected topics.

Real-life Applicability and Experiential Basis

Saturn recognized the Homeroom Guidance program's benefits based on its real-life applicability. An emergent theme emphasized the significance of topics that resonate with students' daily experiences, contributing to the program's perceived effectiveness.

Yes, beneficial *siya* because most of the topics are applicable in their day-to-day real life based on the experiences of the students (Lines 264-265).

Yes, it is beneficial because most topics apply to students' daily lives based on their experiences

In the following paragraphs, I have explored the emergent themes, focusing on Saturn's coping mechanisms in implementing Homeroom Guidance.

Guidance Counselor Facilitation and Resource Access

Saturn's coping mechanisms highlighted the crucial role of the guidance counselor in facilitating the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program. Providing essential resources and orientation sessions emerged as a theme, emphasizing the importance of support systems in overcoming challenges.

Our guidance counselor forwarded the link to us as our softcopy. We also received an orientation related to the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program through our school guidance counselor to guide us on how to conduct the Homeroom Guidance (Lines 268-271).

Resourceful Collaboration for Program Enhancement

Saturn's response highlighted the importance of resourceful collaboration among co-teachers to address challenges in implementing

the Homeroom Guidance Program. The utilization of multimedia presentations and the sharing of video lessons reflect an innovative approach, emphasizing the importance of resourcefulness and collaborative efforts in enhancing the program's effectiveness.

Since there was a shortage of modules printed before, there were teachers who were sharing multimedia presentations on the Homeroom Guidance Program. This has helped to lessen our expenses sa papel. So, *nag download si teacher gamit ang iba't-ibang video lessons maraming makita sa Youtube actually*. So, the resourcefulness of the teachers helped a lot (Lines 274-278).

Since there was a shortage of printed modules before, some teachers shared multimedia presentations on the Homeroom Guidance Program. Thus, it helped reduce our paper expenses. So, a teacher downloaded various video lessons that were available on YouTube. The resourcefulness of the teachers truly made a significant impact.

Stakeholder Collaboration for Resourceful Implementation

Saturn's response emphasized the pivotal role of external stakeholders in contributing to the successful implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program. The theme underscored the importance of collaboration with stakeholders, particularly regarding resource provision and budget allocation, as essential to overcoming implementation challenges.

Yes Ma'am, *pwede maka-help ang mga stakeholders*. By providing materials such as bond paper or budget *para magkaroon ng* one is to one ratio ng module per *bata* (Lines 282-284).

Yes, Ma'am, stakeholders can help by providing materials such as bond paper or budget to ensure a one-to-one ratio of modules per student.

Enhancing Engagement through Multimedia Integration

Saturn's response emphasized the significance of multimedia tools, particularly video lessons, to enhance student engagement and prevent monotony. The emergent theme emphasized the importance of dynamic interactions in the Guidance Program, explicitly focusing on multimedia integration as the best practice for successful implementation.

Ang isa sa mga best practices para hindi ma-bored ang mga bata, I used multi-media or the video lesson, *yun talaga..kasi if more on reading lang walang ano dapat ganun kasi ang student-teacher interaction. Naga-based sa video na pinapanood, isa rin yan para successful ang pag-implement ng Guidance Program* (Lines 287-291).

One of the best practices for keeping the students engaged is using multimedia or video lessons. Thus, it is effective because if the lesson focuses on reading, there will be little student-teacher interaction. Basing it on the videos they watch is also one key to successfully implementing the Guidance Program.

Strategic Time Allocation and Priority Setting

Saturn's coping strategy revolved around strategic time allocation and prioritizing Homeroom Guidance. The emergent theme underscored the importance of adhering to a set schedule despite challenges from other subjects and strategically managing time to ensure a dedicated focus on the program's implementation.

Always *balik sa schedule sa teacher's program*, since *andyan ang Homeroom Guidance kailangan mai-implement talaga for one hour*. Sometimes *kasi yung lesson for Homeroom Guidance since mayron na hinahabol from other subject nagagawa siyang pantapal minsan. Kay ang Homeroom Guidance wait muna ito muna* (Lines 293-297).

Always refer back to the teacher's schedule because that is where Homeroom Guidance is allocated and needs to be implemented for one hour. Sometimes, the lesson for Homeroom Guidance gets squeezed in as a patchwork solution because there are other subjects to catch up on. So, the Homeroom Guidance has to wait its turn.

At this juncture, I explored the emerging themes that captured the insights from Saturn's experiential journey in implementing Homeroom Guidance.

Engagement through Relatable Topics and Module Accessibility

Saturn's experiences suggested that engagement in Homeroom Guidance is influenced by the relatability of topics to students. The emergent theme underscored the need for topics that resonate with students' interests and experiences. Additionally, the challenge of module availability pointed to the importance of ensuring equal access to materials for effective program implementation.

Depende kasi sa topic, if hindi ganun ka-interesting minsan nabo-bored ang bata. Kay usually makarelata talaga ang mga bata. Ang difficulty lang sa implementation is lack of modules for the learners para isa-isa (Lines 301-303).

It depends on the topic; sometimes, the students get bored if it could be more enjoyable. Usually, the students can relate well. The difficulty in implementation lies in the need for modules for the learners, one for each.

Overcoming Challenges Amidst School Activities

Saturn's experiences suggested an emergent theme of overcoming challenges in maintaining consistent Homeroom Guidance sessions amidst the impact of various school activities. The theme underscored the need for strategies to address scheduling conflicts and prioritize program implementation despite external demands.

Same lang naman po. Compared sa first implementation nya, medyo na lessen ang pagconduct ng Homeroom Guidance due to many different school activities na kailangan habulin. *Ganyan...same with other subjects hindi na talaga nadi-discuss kasi may mga school activities, hehe...sa schedule yun ang isa sa problema* (Lines 311-315).

It is just the same. Compared to the first implementation, the conduct of Homeroom Guidance has been reduced due to many different school activities that must be attended to. The same is true for other subjects; they cannot be discussed because of school activities. That is one of the problems in the schedule.

Evolution of Teacher Self-Perception

Saturn's experiences highlighted an emergent theme centered around the evolution of the teacher's self-perception. This theme underscored the transformative journey of gaining a deeper understanding of oneself and an enhanced awareness of learners' characteristics. It reflected a shift in mindset and a recognition of the teacher's potential to impact students positively.

Self-awareness as a teacher based sa result ng kanilang activities na more pa in getting to know the learners. *At mas nadagdagang pa ay kaya pala ganito siya* *Lines 318-320).

Self-awareness as a teacher is based on the results of their activities, and it's more about getting to know the learners. What's been added is understanding why they are like this.

Pedagogical Evolution: Fostering Creativity and Diversity

Saturn's experiences revealed an emergent theme centered around the evolution of pedagogical views. This theme signified a shift towards enhanced creativity in designing activities and recognizing the importance of catering to diverse learning styles. It underscored a commitment to engaging, age-appropriate teaching methods that fostered a dynamic and inclusive learning environment.

I became more creative based on every activity. As a teacher, I need to give more activities na related sa kanilang age. Different learning styles, different strategies. *Hindi pwede na same activities lang ang gagawin mo* to be more creative para mas makuha or ma-catch mo ang interest nila (Lines 323-326).

Based on every activity, I became more creative. As a teacher, I need to provide more activities related to their age. They have different learning styles and strategies. It is not acceptable to do the same activities to be more creative so we can capture their interest.

Enhancing Homeroom Guidance Oversight

The emergent theme of "Enhancing Homeroom Guidance Oversight" highlighted the crucial need for a more robust monitoring and supervisory system to ensure the effective implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program. Saturn's insights shed light on the need for more stringent oversight challenges. Her observation is that not all topics are discussed and that a shortage of modules points to potential gaps in the program's execution.

Saturn's perspective highlighted the importance of administrative involvement in addressing these deficiencies. A more proactive approach to monitoring, involving regular check-ins, assessments, and feedback mechanisms, could significantly contribute to overcoming the challenges identified. This theme emphasized the necessity for educational institutions to prioritize the Homeroom Guidance Program and invest in comprehensive oversight mechanisms to maximize its impact on students' personal and academic development.

Saturn's experiences contributed to an emergent theme focused on enhancing oversight for the Homeroom Guidance Program. The theme emphasized the crucial role of strict administration monitoring to ensure the program's comprehensive implementation. It reflects a commitment to optimizing the impact of Homeroom Guidance in guiding students toward holistic development.

Insights? Learnings? Since as I have said not all topics in Homeroom Guidance can be discussed, maybe I have learned that the administration must strictly monitor this Homeroom Guidance Program Implementation. *Opo, yun kasi yung napansin ko kasi kulang. Ay kasi wala naming monitoring ay ok lang yan hindi na lang ituro. Kasi Homeroom Guidance is very important dito natin malalaman ang personal and academic development ng bata. Kaya kapag ma-implement ito ng Mabuti, ang bata ay nasa right path talaga. Since kulang man ang strict monitoring nito, yun po. I hope sana magkaroon na talaga ng strict monitoring si admin para mas maimplement ng Mabuti ang Homeroom Guidance* (Lines 328-336).

Insights? Learnings? As we mentioned, not all topics in Homeroom Guidance can be discussed. We have learned that the administration must rigorously monitor the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program. Yes, that is what we noticed because it is lacking. Without monitoring, it is okay, but it is better not to teach it. Homeroom Guidance is very important; this is where we learn about the personal and academic development of the child. So, when implemented well, the child is on the right

path. Since there is a lack of strict monitoring, that is it. The administration should indeed have strict monitoring to implement Homeroom Guidance effectively.

Table 3. *The Thematic Analysis of Saturn’s Challenges, Coping Mechanisms, and Insights Learned in the Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program*

<i>Clustered Theme</i>	<i>Emergent Theme</i>
<i>Challenges</i>	
Incomplete reproduction of modules implementation Overwhelming activities during face-to-face classes Challenges in Module Availability Scheduling Constraint Selective Implementation Limited time	Reproduction Challenges and Struggling Balance Time Limitations and Selective Focus
<i>Copings</i>	
Guidance Counselor Support Softcopy Link Orientation Sessions The Homeroom Guidance program is viewed positively Most topics are relatable to learners Module Shortage Mitigation Cost Reduction Resourcefulness and Collaboration Stakeholder Support Resource Provision Budget Allocation Utilization of Multimedia Student-Teacher Interaction Guidance Program Implementation Adherence to Schedule Prioritization of Homeroom Guidance Strategic Time Management Adherence to School Program Affirmative View Real-life Applicability Experiential Basis	Guidance Counselor Facilitation and Resource Access Positive Perception of HRGP Resourceful Collaboration for Program Enhancement Stakeholder Collaboration for Resourceful Implementation Enhancing Engagement through Multimedia Integration Strategic Time Allocation and Priority Setting Real-life Applicability and Experiential Basis
<i>Insights</i>	
Interest-dependent Engagement Relatability as a Key Factor Consistency in Implementation Challenges in Conducting Sessions Impact of School Activities on Homeroom Guidance Enhanced Self-Awareness Deeper Understanding of Learners Revelation of Capabilities Enhanced Creativity Recognition of Diverse Learning Styles Importance of Engaging Activities Strict Monitoring for Effective Implementation Crucial Role in Personal and Academic Development Insights on Program Oversight	Engagement through Relatable Topics Overcoming Challenges Amidst School Activities Evolution of Teacher Self-Perception Pedagogical Evolution: Fostering Creativity and Diversity Enhancing Homeroom Guidance Oversight

7. CASE 4 – MILKY WAY

In Chapter 8, I explored the experiences of another educator, whom I shall refer to as Milky Way, as she passed through the challenges and triumphs encountered in implementing the Homeroom Guidance program. Milky Way, a dedicated teacher, shared insights into her journey, shedding light on the unique obstacles in her classroom. This chapter comprehensively explored the emergent themes surrounding Milky Way's experiences, coping mechanisms, and the valuable lessons she has gleaned from her involvement in the Homeroom Guidance program. Through her narrative, we gained a deeper understanding of the program's impact on teachers and students, contributing to the broader conversation on the significance of holistic education.

In the upcoming paragraphs, I explored the various themes that have surfaced in Milky Way's experiences during the implementation of Homeroom Guidance.

Limited Parental Involvement and Literacy Barriers

The emergent theme of "Limited Parental and Literacy Barriers" in Milky Way's challenges highlighted a significant obstacle in implementing the Homeroom Guidance program. Milky Way expressed concern over the parents' response to assigned activities, explicitly noting the challenges posed by illiterate parents. This limitation in literacy skills hindered their ability to engage with and respond to the assigned tasks for their children. The theme underscored the importance of considering parents' diverse backgrounds and abilities, emphasizing the need for alternative approaches and resources to ensure effective communication and engagement in the Homeroom Guidance program.

Actually, it's only one the parents' response to the different activities as per suggested in the Homeroom Guidance *ky may mga ibang parents na illiterate. Kung ano ang binigay mo na activities sa kanila ganun pa rin wala talagang sagot dahil wala rin silang kakayanan na sagutan ang mga activities na assignment ng mga anak nila* (Lines 340-344).

It is only one of the parents' responses to the different activities suggested in the Homeroom Guidance because some parents are illiterate. Whatever activities we give them, they are still the same; there are no answers because they cannot also answer the activities assigned to their children.

Consistent Commitment to Homeroom Guidance Implementation

Milky Way emphasized the crucial variable influencing the incorporation of Homeroom Guidance into regular classroom routines—consistency and commitment. The phrases highlighted the need to approach the program with a dedicated mindset, religiously adhering to the suggested schedules, and making Homeroom Guidance a routine practice. This emergent theme stressed the significance of a teacher's steadfast commitment to consistently implementing Homeroom Guidance, ensuring its integration into regular classroom activities.

It's about doing the Homeroom Guidance religiously, following what is suggested kung mayroon mang schedule doon you have to follow it. Hindi yung kung kailan mo lang naalala doon ka lng magHomeroom Guidance. *Kapag mag-Homeroom Guidance kay I see to it na gagawin mo talaga siya. Gawin mo siyang routinary* and there must be a commitment (Lines 348-352).

It is about doing the Homeroom Guidance religiously, following what is suggested if there is a schedule; we have to follow it. Not just when we remember it; that is when we do the Homeroom Guidance. When doing Homeroom Guidance, I make sure that we do it. Make it a routine, and there must be a commitment.

Program Design Impression and Barriers in Parental Attitudes

Milky Way appreciated the Homeroom Guidance Program's design, considering it impressive, with a clear task list. However, she acknowledged barriers posed by parental attitudes, mainly those illiterates. The theme emphasized the dual aspects of the program—its well-thought-out design and the challenges arising from parental attitudes. Despite being an excellent design, the program faces hindrances when parents, especially those with literacy issues, become obstacles. This emergent theme emphasized the importance of recognizing both program implementation's positive aspects and challenges.

Actually, I like the program *kasi nakalagay na doon lahat kung ano ang gagawin mo. Naka-itemized na siya lahat. Si Teacher mag-implement na lang gyud si teacher. Pero yun pa rin yung mga ano doon mga barriers like the attitude ni parents kay dili man siya pwede na si bata lang mismo. Actually, the whole program is very impressive hawud kayo ang nakahuna-huna sa iya pero how about those parent na illiterate additional burden na pud to kay teacher. "Mother, nganong wla man ni siya ingon ani kay sayang ni?" "Ma'am busy man gud mi dili namo ma-assist amoang bata." So si parent na pud ang maka-hinder sa program. Perfect design siya para sa mga FL* (Lines 356-364).

I like the program because everything we need to do is outlined there. It is all itemized. The teacher needs to implement it. However, there are still barriers, such as the parents' attitude, because it is not just about the child. The whole program is awe-inspiring; we thought of it, but what about those parents who are illiterate? It is an additional burden for the teacher. 'Mother, why isn't it like this? It is a waste.' 'Ma'am, we are busy; we cannot assist our child.' So, the parents can also hinder the program. It is a perfect design for FL.

Parent-Child Relationship Development Through Homeroom Guidance

Milky Way highlighted the program's benefit in developing the relationship between parents and children. She specifically mentioned Grade 1 outputs that demonstrated bonding between parents and students. The emergent theme stressed the positive impact of Homeroom Guidance in fostering stronger connections within families. By emphasizing the significance of parent-child relationships, the theme reflected the broader positive influence of the program beyond academic aspects. It echoed the idea that Homeroom Guidance catalyzes family engagement and bonding.

Yes, beneficial. It would develop the parent and the child relationship. *Sa amoa sa Grade 1 Ma'am naa mi mga output na magbond si parent. Is ana siya sa mga beneficial pud* (Lines 367-369).

Yes, it is beneficial. It would develop the parent and child relationship. In our Grade 1, Ma'am, we have outputs where the parent and child bond. It is one of the beneficial aspects as well.

At this juncture, I probed a comprehensive exploration of the various themes that have surfaced in the Coping Mechanisms employed by Milky Way during the implementation of Homeroom Guidance.

School Head Collaboration and Home Visits as Coping Strategies

Milky Way employed a collaborative approach by regularly discussing learner outputs with the school head and seeking support and valuable input from the office. This partnership is a crucial coping mechanism, providing her with guidance and resources to address obstacles in implementing Homeroom Guidance. Additionally, her active engagement through home visits to learners demonstrates a hands-on approach to overcoming challenges. The emergent theme emphasized the significance of collaborative efforts with school leadership and direct interactions with students at their homes, showcasing the importance of a multifaceted strategy to navigate impediments in implementing the program.

Whenever I opened up to the school head regarding the learners' output, we could receive support like inputs from the office. Then, we visit our learner's home (Lines 372-374).

Lack of Collaborative Innovation and Initiative

Milky Way highlighted a notable absence of collaborative innovations or initiatives among co-teachers to address challenges related to Homeroom Guidance. The phrases suggested a decentralized approach, each teacher combating the issues individually. The emergent theme underscored the need for a more collective and proactive effort, indicating a potential area for improvement within the teaching community. Collaboration and shared initiatives could enhance the effectiveness of the Homeroom Guidance program, fostering a more supportive and innovative teaching environment.

Wala man innovations, wala man nag-initiate. Kanaya kanya na lang (Lines 377).

There must be more innovations and initiatives; each operates in collaboration.

Influence of External Variables on Homeroom Guidance Implementation

Milky Way acknowledged the potential impact of external variables, such as administrative rules and community dynamics, on the challenges faced in implementing Homeroom Guidance. The importance of tapping into stakeholders for support emerges as a key phrase, highlighting the need for collaboration with external entities to address these challenges effectively. The emergent theme underscored the significance of considering and directing external factors in the planning and executing of the Homeroom Guidance program, emphasizing the role of a broader community approach in ensuring its success.

Yes, it is possible. Tapping our stakeholders would be very helpful in implementing Homeroom Guidance (Lines 381-382).

Positive Reinforcement and Feedback in Homeroom Guidance Program

Milky Way emphasized the importance of positive reinforcement and feedback as a best practice in implementing Homeroom Guidance. The phrases highlighted her approach to rewarding and appreciating children's performances, creating a positive and supportive environment. The theme emphasized the role of encouragement, acknowledgment, and constructive feedback in fostering a conducive atmosphere for learning and engagement. By employing these practices, Milky Way motivated the students and established a connection that encourages active participation and continuous involvement in the Homeroom Guidance Program.

One of my best practices is rewarding them and giving positive feedback. I see to it that I appreciate the child's performance. I always say "Wow, very good! *Nakapasa gyud ka, very good gyud imong Mama. Palngga gyud ka sa imong Mama!*" *Giana-ana gyud nako kinsa man kauban nimo nag-answer ani? Moingon dayon ang bata na akoang Mama. Wow, very good gyud mo ni Mama nimo!*" *It's a matter of hug and tapping their shoulders. Siguro isa na sa akoang best practices that is why ang mga bata makakit sa akong moduol lng gihapon. Pero there are also time na gina-correct pud nako unsa ang mali. Gina-ingon gyud dayon nako unsa ang mali* (Lines 385-393).

One of the most effective practices involves the implementation of positive reinforcement and constructive feedback. We ensure that we express genuine appreciation for a child's performance by consistently acknowledging their achievements. We often exclaim, "Wow, very good! We passed; our Mama must be very proud. Our Mama loves us so much!" In doing so, we create a connection, making the child feel they are with their mother. This practice involves a combination of hugs and gentle taps on their shoulders. It may be one of the standout practices so the children feel comfortable approaching us. However, it is essential to note that there are times when we also provide corrections, promptly addressing any mistakes and guiding them toward improvement.

Compassionate Coping and Self-Care in Homeroom Guidance Challenges

Milky Way's coping strategy involved approaching challenges with compassion, an open heart, and a deep understanding of the learners' nature. The phrases highlighted the importance of empathy and a caring attitude in managing difficulties related to Homeroom Guidance. Additionally, Milky Way emphasized the significance of self-care, creating a balance by indulging in personal activities like reading books and watching movies. The emergent theme underscored the role of compassion and self-care as coping mechanisms for the teacher and as essential components in maintaining a positive and supportive environment for both the teacher and the learners.

This approach contributed to the overall well-being of the teacher and, consequently, enhanced the effectiveness of the Homeroom Guidance program.

Deal with it with compassion and open heart and a matter of understanding the nature of our learners. Use your heart. I do Self-care, I love to read books and watch movies and just stay inside my room and simply have peace. My comfort zone is my bedroom. Kung walang self-care paano nya i-extend sa uban (Lines 395-399).

Approach it with compassion and an open heart, grounded in a deep understanding of the nature of our learners. Truly engage with the task using our heart. I prioritize self-care, finding solace in activities such as reading books, watching movies, and spending quiet moments inside the room to achieve peace. The sanctuary is the bedroom, and extending genuine care to others is challenging without self-care.

The following paragraphs outline diverse themes arising from the invaluable insights from Milky Way's journey in implementing Homeroom Guidance.

Parental Involvement and Literacy Challenges

Milky Way's experiences highlighted the dual challenges of dealing with illiterate parents and those who are unable to support their children academically due to work commitments. The difficulties underscored the importance of addressing literacy barriers and finding ways to engage parents with limited availability. On the positive side, the achievements emphasized the impact of Homeroom Guidance in fostering responsive parents who, in turn, contributed to a supportive community. The emergent theme emphasized the crucial role of parental involvement in the success of the Homeroom Guidance program, recognizing that addressing literacy challenges and encouraging active participation can lead to a more effective and inclusive educational experience for the learners.

Mga difficulties I have encountered was dealing with illiterate parents who cannot provide support to the academics of their children. Also, parents who cannot give time to their children due to work. The achievements are having responsive parents who are also helping other parents (Lines 403-406).

The difficulties I have encountered include dealing with illiterate parents who are unable to support their children's academics. Additionally, some parents cannot dedicate time to their children due to work commitments. On the positive side, the achievements include having responsive parents who actively support not only their children but also assist other parents.

Adaptation and Creativity in Implementation

Milky Way's experiences highlighted the dynamic nature of implementing the Homeroom Guidance Program, emphasizing the need for teachers to test various approaches. The phrase "testing the waters" suggested a willingness to adapt and find strategies that vibrate with both teachers and parents. The evolving process involved becoming more creative in addressing challenges and ensuring that the program is embraced effectively. The emergent theme underscored the importance of adaptability and creativity in implementing Homeroom Guidance, reflecting a continuous effort to refine and enhance the program's impact on educators and parents.

You have to test the waters man gud. Si teacher need gyud magtry ug different approaches. Mag-isip gyud c teacher sa iya buhaton na paano nila ni i-embrace ning Homeroom Guidance Program. So, check n apud na to if tam aba n inga approach sa mga parents. I have become more creative kanang makasabot gyud gani sila (Lines 409-413).

You have to test the waters. The teacher needs to try different approaches and think about how to make the Homeroom Guidance Program embraced by the parents. So, check if the approach resonates with the parents. I have become more creative, ensuring that they truly understand.

Patience and Understanding for Transformation

Milky Way's response highlighted the conscious effort to upgrade patience as a significant aspect of her evolving method and mindset. The phrase "upgrading patience" suggested a deliberate intention to enhance this attribute. The focus on realizing goals indicated a goal-oriented approach to teaching, where patience becomes a vital tool for achieving desired outcomes. Furthermore, the emphasis on extending understanding reflected a compassionate perspective, recognizing the challenges teachers and parents face. The emergent theme underscored the transformative power of patience and understanding in navigating challenges and fostering positive outcomes in implementing the Homeroom Guidance Program.

Gi-upgrade gyud nako akoang pasensya, hehe. Tama ba ko Ma'am? Gi-upgrade gyud nako akoang patience para ma-ano ma-materialized akoang gusto mahitabo, marealize akoang gusto mahitabo. I-extend gyud nimo imo pasensya. Luoy kayo sila (Lines 416-419).

I upgraded my patience, hehe. Am I right, Ma'am? I upgraded my patience to make my aspirations happen and realize what I want to happen. You have to extend your patience. It is pitiful.

Student-Centric Pedagogy and Approachability

Milky Way's response emphasized the importance of adopting a student-centric pedagogical approach, as indicated by the phrase

"stepping down to their level." Thus, it implied a recognition of the need to connect with students on a personal and relatable level, transcending formal titles or academic achievements. The desire to be approachable and unthreatening, reflected in the statement "I do not mention my position," underscored the value placed on creating a conducive and comfortable student environment. The overarching emergent theme is the commitment to student well-being and a teaching philosophy centered around being approachable, understanding, and prioritizing the needs of the students in the classroom.

Kahit pa graduate ka na ng master's or doctoral, you need to step down to their level. Dili gyud pwede na master ko, dili gyud pwede na doctor na ko. Master teacher na ko. I do not mention my position. I want to establish an approachable ko ana dili sila ma-intimidate sa akoa that they can ask me anything. Na love nako inyong anak that once naa sila sa akoang classroom they are safe. Above anything else sila akoang priority. Kapag naa ko sa school, naa ra gyud ko sa classroom (Line 422-428).

Even if we have a master's or doctoral degree, we need to step down to their level. It is unacceptable to say that being a master, a doctor, a master teacher, not to mention the position, and to establish that being approachable means that they will not be intimidated by me and that they can ask anything. I love our children; they are safe once in the classroom. Above anything else, they should be the priority. When at school, they will find us in the classroom.

Holistic Development through Timely and Essential Guidance

Milky Way's response highlighted the significance of Homeroom Guidance in promoting holistic development. The phrases "timely and essential" emphasized the program's relevance and importance. The statement "a great help to teachers" underscored the positive impact on educators, suggesting that the benefits extend beyond students. The phrase "teaching life skills" pointed to the practical and valuable aspects of the guidance program in imparting essential skills for daily living. The emergent theme encapsulated the idea that Homeroom Guidance contributes not only to academic learning but also to the overall development of students, fostering a well-rounded and responsible approach to life.

About the insight sa Homeroom Guidance, beneficial siya. *Kanang timely siya and above all things dako siya help ky teacher, si teacher gyud ang maka-benefit sa HRGP ky actually kanang ahhh kay kanang kuan ahhh great help siya kay teacher. 7:15-7:55am. Essential siya though extra work siya sa parent but this time, si bata pud makatuon gyud sila like following schedules like fixing their beds, teaching them with life skills (Lines 430-435).*

The insight on homeroom guidance is beneficial. It is timely, and, above all, it greatly helps the teacher. The teacher benefits from HRGP because it's a great help to the teacher. From 7:15 to 7:55 a.m., it is essential, though it adds extra work for parents. However, the children also learn this time, such as following schedules and developing life skills like fixing their beds.

Table 4. *The Thematic Analysis of Milky Way's Challenges, Copings, and Insights Learned in the Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program*

<i>Challenges</i>	<i>Clustered Theme</i>	<i>Emergent Theme</i>
Inability to answer assignments		Limited Parental Involvement and Literacy Barriers
Parent's response to activities		
Illiterate parents		Barriers to Parental Attitudes
Barriers like parental attitudes		
Copings		School Head Collaboration and Home Visits as Coping Strategies
Open up to the school head.		
Receive support and input from the office		
Conduct home visits to learners		Influence of External Variables on Homeroom Guidance Implementation
External variables impact implementation		
Tapping stakeholders is crucial		
Administrative rules and community dynamics matter		Positive Reinforcement and Feedback in Homeroom Guidance
Rewarding and giving positive feedback		
Appreciating the child's performance		
Correcting mistakes with feedback		Compassionate Coping and Self-Care in Homeroom Guidance Challenges
Deal with compassion and an open heart		
Self-care as a coping mechanism		
Understanding the nature of learners		
<i>Insights</i>		
Dealing with illiterate parents		Parental Involvement and Literacy Challenges
Parents unable to provide academic support		
Achievements with responsive parents		Adaptation and Creativity in Implementation
Testing different approaches		
Becoming more creative		
Embracing the Homeroom Guidance Program		Patience and Understanding for Transformation
Upgrading patience		
Realizing goals		

Extending understanding	
Stepping down to their level	
Approachable and unthreatening	Student-Centric Pedagogy and Approachability
Priority to students	
Timely and essential	
Great help to teachers	Holistic Development through Timely and Essential Guidance
Teaching life skills	
Doing the Homeroom Guidance religiously	
Following suggested schedules	Consistent Commitment to Homeroom Guidance Implementation
Making Homeroom Guidance routine with commitment	
Impressive program design	Program Design Impression
Develop parent and child relationship.	
Grade 1 outputs show parental bonding.	Parent-Child Relationship Development Through Homeroom Guidance

8. CASE 5 – MERCURY

This chapter discusses the case of Mercury and the unique experiences and challenges she faced as a dedicated educator in implementing the Homeroom Guidance Program. Mercury's insights provided valuable perspectives on the intricate interplay between the program and the diverse realities within the classroom setting. Through Mercury's narrative, we gained a deeper understanding of the hurdles encountered and the innovative strategies employed to navigate them. This chapter sheds light on the dynamic relationship between educators, students, and the Homeroom Guidance Program, offering valuable insights for those seeking to enhance the effectiveness of this transformative educational initiative.

In the following sections, I explored various themes that have surfaced regarding the challenges faced by Mercury in the implementation of Homeroom Guidance.

Linguistic Challenges and Time Constraints

Implementing the Homeroom Guidance Program posed significant challenges for Mercury, particularly in the context of language and time constraints. The initial hurdle involved translating the program into the vernacular to effectively communicate with students, emphasizing the importance of linguistic adaptation for successful implementation. Additionally, the limited time allocation of 30 minutes per week becomes a substantial barrier, hindering the comprehensive discussion of the program's guidelines. These challenges underscored the need to address linguistic diversity and reconsider time allotments to enhance the efficacy of the Homeroom Guidance Program in Mercury's classroom.

Homeroom Guidance is very challenging to implement especially in the class ahhh so far because ahhh... the language or the medium of instruction is in English. But ah...so the challenges ah...the first challenge for the teachers in the lower grades is that they need to translate HG to vernacular or the mother tongue. and afterward, the #2 challenge is time. Maybe 30 minutes is not enough in the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program. Though, one-week xa pero 30 minutes every day. No, one hour per week lng siya. So, the time is not enough to discuss what is in the guidelines of the HRGP (Lines 439-447).

Homeroom Guidance is challenging to implement, especially in the classroom, primarily because the medium of instruction is English. The initial challenge for teachers in the lower grades involves translating Homeroom Guidance into the vernacular or the mother tongue. Subsequently, the second challenge is time constraints. Allocating only 30 minutes each day for the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program poses difficulties. Despite spanning a week, more than the limited time frame of one hour per week is needed to cover the guidelines outlined in the HRGP comprehensively. These challenges highlight the need for effective strategies to address language barriers and time limitations to enhance the successful execution of the Homeroom Guidance Program.

Classroom and Time Management

Mercury emphasized the critical role of discipline and classroom management as vital variables influencing the successful integration of Homeroom Guidance activities into regular classroom routines. Maintaining a disciplined environment ensures a conducive atmosphere for the effective implementation of the program. Moreover, time management is crucial, especially since Homeroom Guidance is typically scheduled as the first period. Balancing these elements becomes imperative to seamlessly incorporate Homeroom Guidance into the daily classroom routine, emphasizing the need for structured discipline and efficient time utilization.

Ahhh sa kuan sa classroom gyud? The discipline or the classroom management and time management. Then, usually man gud ang Homeroom Guidance naa man gud siya sa first period of classes (Lines 451-453).

It is in the classroom. It involves discipline, classroom management, and time management. Homeroom Guidance is usually conducted during the first period of classes.

Motivation and Lack of Support

Mercury expressed a positive attitude towards the Homeroom Guidance Program and a genuine willingness to participate. However, a significant challenge arises from the school administration's need for more support and monitoring. Despite the teacher's enthusiasm

and readiness to confront the program's challenges, the lack of institutional motivation hampers the overall effectiveness of Homeroom Guidance implementation. The emergent theme highlighted the crucial role that administrative support plays in fostering motivation and overcoming challenges associated with the program.

Ganahan ko sa Homeroom Guidance Program and willing but then... mao lagi na walay support from the school, from the admin. You are not motivated to do it ky wala man monitoring (Lines 457-459).

I like the Homeroom Guidance Program and am willing to participate, but there needs to be more support from the school or the administration. We are not motivated to do it because there is no monitoring.

Discipline and Behavioral Changes

Mercury strongly believed in the benefits of the Homeroom Guidance Program, particularly in addressing the discipline of children, which he notes has shifted over time. He highlighted the contemporary challenge of waning respect among children but saw the potential for a positive transformation by implementing Homeroom Guidance. The emergent theme stressed the program's potential impact on instilling discipline and fostering positive behavioral changes in students, aligning with the evolving needs of the present generation.

Beneficial siya, very beneficial especially nowadays and disiplina sa mga bata dili na pareha sang una. Sang-una respectful ang mga bata pero karon dili na kayo, hehehe..Pero kung iimplement ang Homeroom Guidance siguro mabalik man siguro (Lines 462-465).

It is very beneficial, especially nowadays, when children's discipline is not as strict as it was when they were respectful, but now not so much. However, if homeroom Guidance is implemented, things may improve.

Mercury's approach to implementing Homeroom Guidance revealed several effective coping mechanisms, shedding light on strategic and adaptive measures employed to overcome challenges and ensure the successful execution of the program.

Evolving Support Systems

Mercury reflected on the support systems during the pandemic, acknowledging the initial provision of materials crucial for Homeroom Guidance. However, he noted a decline in sustained support afterward. Homeroom guidance tools are included in official documents like Form 137, and the Learner Development Assessment Tool signals an emergent theme. This theme revolved around the evolving nature of support systems, with positive and challenging aspects emphasizing the need for consistent resources to sustain effective Homeroom Guidance implementation.

Adtong pandemic time naa siya. There were provisions of materials pero afterwards wala na. Where in fact ang nakabutang sa amoang Form 137 sa unahan ang Homeroom Guidance, yung Learner Development Assessment Tool (Lines 468-470).

It was present during the pandemic. There were provisions of materials, but afterward, there were none. Initially placed in our Form 137 was the Homeroom Guidance, specifically the Learner Development Assessment Tool.

Collaborative Resource Provision

Mercury highlighted a straightforward yet impactful tactic co-teachers employ – the provision of materials. The simplicity of this approach, as expressed by "It is easier for the teacher," underscores its effectiveness. The emergent theme revolved around concerted efforts among teachers to address challenges related to Homeroom Guidance. This theme emphasized the importance of sharing resources to simplify implementation and create a supportive environment within the teaching community.

Provision of materials. Kay dali na lng kay teachers eh (Lines 473).

Provision of materials. It is just easier for teachers.

External Variables Impact

Mercury acknowledged the influence of external variables, specifically administrative rules and community dynamics, in the challenges faced during Homeroom Guidance implementation. The importance of these external factors is captured in the phrase "They are contributors," signifying their role in shaping the program's context. The emergent theme highlighted the need for adequate administrative support, including precise monitoring mechanisms and the provision of essential materials. It emphasized that successful Homeroom Guidance implementation requires harmoniously aligning with external variables, emphasizing partnership between educators and stakeholders.

Contributors man sila. Possible. Para sa monitoring and admin.Kung walay mga provision of materials kay wala pwede i-tap ang stakeholders (Lines 477-478).

They are contributors. Monitoring and administration are possible. If there are no provisions for materials, stakeholders cannot be involved.

Effective Practices and Recognition

Mercury highlighted two crucial aspects for successful Homeroom Guidance: providing necessary materials in each classroom and monitoring and evaluation. The phrase "Provisions of materials in every classroom" emphasizes the practical need for resources, ensuring that classrooms are equipped for effective implementation. Additionally, the recommendation for a monitoring and evaluation system reflects a commitment to assessing the program's impact and making necessary adjustments.

The emergent theme underscored the value of recognizing and rewarding class advisers for their dedicated implementation efforts. Mercury suggests an "award system if truly be implemented for the class adviser," promoting a positive reinforcement approach to encourage teachers' active engagement in the Homeroom Guidance Program.

For best practices Provision of kuan materials in every classroom. Then, for recommendations-monitoring and evaluation. And award system if truly nag-implement ang class adviser awardan siya eh (Lines 481-483).

Every classroom should have material provisions for best practices. Then, for recommendations, monitoring, and evaluation, an award system should be in place; if a class adviser truly implements a best practice, they should be recognized with an award.

Personal Investment and Resourcefulness

The three phrases highlighted Mercury's commitment and resourcefulness in overcoming challenges. "I printed them all by myself," underscored Mercury's hands-on approach, taking the initiative to print materials personally. The phrase "with my own expense" emphasizes a personal investment, indicating that Mercury is willing to incur costs to ensure the availability of necessary resources. "Bond paper for the learner's activities" further illustrated this dedication, specifying that the expense was directed toward materials for the children's activities.

The emergent theme revolved around Mercury's investment and resourcefulness in managing challenges, reflecting a proactive stance to address obstacles independently and ensure the program's continuity.

Hehehe..Kuan nag ano ko nagprint ko ug akua lang..with my own expense sa kanang bond paper ana para sa mga activities sa mga bata (Lines 485-486).

I did what I printed independently, using the expenses for that bond paper for the children's activities.

I explored various surfaced themes in the concluding paragraphs, highlighting the valuable insights from Mercury's experience implementing homeroom guidance.

Linguistic Challenges and Double Effort

The three phrases highlighted a prevalent difficulty Mercury faced in implementing the Homeroom Guidance Program—the use of English as the medium of instruction. The phrase "Medium of instruction is in English" directly pointed to the linguistic challenge of the chosen language. The subsequent phrases, "Double effort for the teachers" and "Translate this into the mother tongue," emphasized the additional workload on the teacher to translate content into the mother tongue.

The emergent theme revolved around Mercury's linguistic challenges, emphasizing the double effort required to bridge the language gap in effectively delivering Homeroom Guidance. This theme underscored the importance of addressing language barriers to enhance the program's accessibility and impact.

Mao tong difficulties na ang medium of instruction is in English. Ahhh kanang magdouble effort pa si teacher sa pagtranslate sa mother tongue (Lines 490-491).

That is the difficulty when the medium of instruction is English. The teacher has to make extra effort to translate it into the mother tongue.

Evolving Implementation and Enhanced Understanding

The phrases highlighted the evolving nature of Mercury's experience implementing the Homeroom Guidance Program. The statement "Last year, it was implemented during the First Quarter" signifies a specific time frame for the initial implementation, suggesting a recent program introduction. The phrase "Really, there were changes" indicates that modifications or improvements have occurred over time.

The emergent theme centered around the dynamic nature of the implementation process, suggesting that adjustments and changes have been made to enhance the program's effectiveness. The phrase "They were easily understood by the learners this time compared to purely modular distance learning" emphasized a positive outcome, indicating an improved understanding by students in the current setup compared to the previous purely modular distance learning approach. This theme underscored the adaptability and continuous improvement inherent in implementing the Homeroom Guidance Program.

Actually, last year, mga First Quarter lang gyud to siya na implement. Naa gyud siya changes. Mas maintindihan gyud siya sa

bata karon compared atong purely modular distance learning (Lines 494-496).

Last year, it was only implemented during the first quarter. It indeed changed. It is now more understandable for children than our purely modular distance learning.

Enhanced Activity Design and Language Adaptation

The phrases suggested a significant shift in Mercury's approach to the Homeroom Guidance activities. "It is part of the giving of activities in Homeroom Guidance" implies a focus on the design or structure of the activities, indicating a deliberate effort in this aspect. The phrase "There are good activities there" suggested abundant, well-designed activities, emphasizing their quality and effectiveness.

The emergent theme centered around upgrading activity content and structure within the Homeroom Guidance Program. Additionally, "I will do it in English, especially in this subject" indicated a conscious decision to use English in creating these activities, aligning with a specific teaching approach. This theme highlighted Mercury's commitment to refining and adapting the program's components to optimize it:

Naa sa mga giving of activities sa Homeroom Guidance. Daghan nindot didto na mga activities. Himuon ko ni sa English. Himuon ko ni sa subject na ing-ani (Lines 499-501).

It is part of the Homeroom Guidance activities, which have many suitable activities. I will do this in English, in a subject like this.

Nontraditional Teaching Approach

The emergent theme in the response revolved around a shift towards nontraditional teaching methods, guided explicitly by the Homeroom Guidance Program module. The phrase "Nontraditional teaching approach" suggested a departure from conventional teaching practices, indicating a more innovative and adaptive pedagogical perspective. The mention of being "guided by the Homeroom Guidance Program module" highlights the significance of structured guidance, providing teachers with a clear framework for their instructional approach. Additionally, the statement "Simplifying the process for teachers in lesson planning" emphasizes the practical benefit of this approach, indicating a positive impact on the ease and efficiency of lesson planning for educators. Inclusively, the emergent theme emphasized embracing modern, guided, and streamlined teaching methods for a more effective educational experience.

Mas kuan mas dili traditional ang pagtudlo. Kuan man ka guided sa Homeroom Guidance Program module. Dili na maglisod pa ang teachers pangita unsa ang itudlo (Lines 504-506).

Teaching is more nontraditional. The Homeroom Guidance Program module guides teachers, and they no longer struggle to figure out what to teach.

Essential Role of Homeroom Guidance

The essential role of Homeroom Guidance, as illuminated by Mercury's insights, becomes evident in the contemporary educational landscape. In an era dominated by digital distractions and the pervasive influence of gadgets, Homeroom Guidance emerges as a crucial element in guiding students away from the potential pitfalls of excessive screen time. Mercury emphasized the need to instill a sense of responsibility in students, a task efficiently undertaken through the structured guidance provided by the Homeroom Guidance Program. In acknowledging the challenges posed by the prevalence of gadgets, Mercury underscores the program's unique capacity to offer a guided approach, steering students in their actions and fostering a sense of responsibility among them.

Furthermore, Mercury highlighted the comparative advantage of Homeroom Guidance over unguided online interactions, particularly on platforms like Facebook. In an age where social media often lacks the guidance required for positive development, Homeroom Guidance stands out as a dedicated space for shaping responsible behavior. Despite Mercury's acknowledgment that the implementation may not always be massive, the program consistently contributed to cultivating a sense of responsibility among students. Thus, it underscored the indispensable role of Homeroom Guidance in modern education, offering a structured and guided approach that transcends the limitations of unmonitored online engagement.

Insights? Kuan ahhh Homeroom Guidance kailangan gyud na itudlo sa mga bata especially karon ang mga bata more on gadgets. Kung didto sa cellphone sa Facebook, dili man didto ma-guidan ang mga bata .pero sa Homeroom Guidance, guided sila sa ilang buhat. Sa akong ganing unom ka sections, ang akong mga bata mas responsible sa uban. Kay though dili kayo massive ang pag kuan nako sa Homeroom Guidance.usahay makatudlo ko usahay dili pero responsible sila nga mga bata (Lines 508-514).

Insights? In the context of Homeroom Guidance, it is crucial to teach children, especially now when they are more focused on gadgets. They will not be guided there if they are on their cell phones or Facebook. However, in Homeroom Guidance, they are guided in their actions. In six sections, the students are more responsible than others. Even though the approach in Homeroom Guidance is not consistently extensive, sometimes we teach, and sometimes we do not, but they are responsible children.

Table 5. *The Thematic Analysis of Mercury's Challenges, Copings, and Insights Learned in the Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program*

"*Tungod sa sunog na nahitabo last school year (Due to the fire incident that happened last year,*" indicating an external factor that impeded their ability to implement programs fully. Additionally, "Lack of awareness and orientation" underscored a crucial aspect, emphasizing the need for proper communication and guidance from school authorities. The emergent theme reflected the impact of external factors and organizational shortcomings on successfully executing the Homeroom Guidance program at the classroom level.

Wala gyud ko nakabasa sa katong gina-ingon nimo kay ambot lng kung naimplement ba to o wala kay dali ra man gud ko malipat gud. Pero sa karon wala gyud mi naka-implement gyud. Tungod sa sunog na nahitabo last school year ky gabii na mi nagauli. Dili gyud namo maimplement ang tanan na programs. Murag half cook gyud ang mga bata ato. Nainform yata kami pero hindi ko na matandaan. Hindi ko lng bal-an sa higher grade level pero wala gyud mi naka-implement ani ba. There was no awareness or orientation conducted. Maybe this School Year our Guidance Coordinator will remind us of this pero kay very busy man gud na siya. Overworked na kayo pud ang amoang Guidance coordinator (Lines 518-526).

I have yet to read what they are referring to; unsure if it was implemented because they quickly forget. However, we still need to implement it. Thus, it was due to the fire incident that happened last school year that we had to evacuate at night. We could only implement some of the programs. The students were left somewhat unprepared. We might have been informed, but we need help remembering. We know the higher grade levels, but we must implement this. There was no awareness or orientation conducted. Our Guidance Coordinator will remind us of this this school year, but they are swamped. Our Guidance coordinator is overworked as well.

Incorporation of Homeroom Guidance Activities

The emergent theme in Earth's response revolved around the critical variables that hinder incorporating Homeroom Guidance activities into regular classroom routines. The phrase "Lack of orientation and awareness" highlighted the absence of essential information and guidance provided to teachers, contributing to their inability to integrate the program. Earth emphasized the significant variable of "Limited time allocation," indicating a mere 15 minutes allocated for the Homeroom Guidance Program. This constraint directly impacted the capacity to include comprehensive activities within the given timeframe. The emergent theme underscored the interconnected challenges of inadequate orientation, time limitations, and the resultant non-implementation of the Homeroom Guidance program, collectively influencing classroom routines.

Wala gyud nako na implement ang Homeroom Guidance kay aside from wala man ko na-orient, 15 minutes lng ang time allocated sa Homeroom Guidance Program (Lines 530-532).

We have yet to implement the Homeroom Guidance because, aside from not being oriented, only 15 minutes are allocated for the Homeroom Guidance Program.

The Interplay of Attitudes, Orientation, and Scheduling Constraints

The emergent theme in Earth's response revolved around the interplay of attitudes, orientation, and scheduling constraints affecting the Homeroom Guidance Program. "Willingness to participate" indicates a positive inclination toward engaging with the program. However, Earth emphasized the significant obstacle of "Lack of orientation," highlighting the critical need for proper guidance and information dissemination. Additionally, mentioning "Scheduling constraints" underscored the challenge of aligning the program with the available time slots, particularly when considering the afternoon schedule and students returning from other classes. The emergent theme pointed to the importance of addressing orientation gaps and scheduling issues to enhance the willingness of educators to confront the challenges posed by the Homeroom Guidance Program.

Willing man tani kaya lng wala man mi na-orient. And then, gusto ko man unta sa hapon na lng nako i-hold ang mga bata for Homeroom Guidance time kaya lng manguli naman pud ang mga bata ky gikan pa ko sa ibang class. Pag-abot ko in the afternoon wala na cla (Lines 536-539).

I would have been willing, but we needed to be more oriented. Also, we would prefer to hold the students for Homeroom Guidance in the afternoon, but they go home because they come from other classes. By the time I arrive in the afternoon, they are no longer there.

Conditional Belief in the Program's Benefits

The emergent theme in Earth's response centered on a conditional belief in the benefits of the Homeroom Guidance Program, contingent upon specific conditions. The phrase "Conditional belief in the program's benefits" suggested that Earth recognizes the potential advantages of the program under certain circumstances. The emphasis on the need for "Orientation" highlighted the critical role of proper guidance and information dissemination to fully appreciate and implement the program effectively. Additionally, the stipulation of "Sufficient time for implementation" underscored the importance of allocating adequate time and resources to ensure the program's success. The emergent theme underscored the notion that the perceived benefits of the Homeroom Guidance Program are intricately linked to factors such as orientation and time allocation.

Kung iimplement beneficial gyud xa, kung may orientation para kabalo pud mi unsaon paghandle sa mga bata and may enough time (Lines 542-543).

It would be beneficial if implemented, especially with an orientation, so we know how to handle the students and if there's enough time.

The upcoming section explored discussions of various themes concerning Earth's coping mechanisms in implementing Homeroom Guidance.

Lack of implementation with the Homeroom Guidance Program

The participant's succinct response, "Nothing. I am sorry," implied an apparent lack of implementation or engagement with the Homeroom Guidance Program. The phrase "Lack of implementation" reflected the straightforward acknowledgment that the program had not been implemented. The participant's tone, suggested by the words "Implicit frustration or disinterest," hinted at a potential lack of enthusiasm or frustration regarding the program. The response raises the possibility of "Possible external obstacles" contributing to the non-implementation, such as time constraints, lack of awareness, or administrative challenges. The emergent theme suggested a significant gap or hindrance in Earth's coping mechanisms related to the Homeroom Guidance Program, indicating a need for further exploration and resolution.

Potential Gap in Communication and Collaboration among Teachers

The participant's response emphasized the need for external support, as indicated by the phrase "Belief in the need for external support." Thus, it suggested that the participant recognized the significance of assistance from external sources in addressing challenges related to the Homeroom Guidance Program. The acknowledgment of administrative influence is compressed in the phrase "Acknowledgment of administrative influence," indicating an understanding of administrative rules' role in shaping the program's implementation. Furthermore, "Importance of community awareness" highlighted the participant's recognition that community dynamics are crucial, underscoring the need to inform and involve the community in supporting the Homeroom Guidance Program. The emergent theme revolved around the participant's call for comprehensive external support, encompassing administrative and community engagement, to enhance the program's effectiveness.

Wala gyud ko nabal-an na innovations especially on our Grade level. Hindi ko lng bal-an sa uban na Grade levels (Lines 549-550).

I am still learning about innovations, especially at our grade level. We have yet to learn about other grade levels.

The Call for Comprehensive External Support

The participant's response emphasized the need for external support, as indicated by the phrase "Belief in the need for external support." Thus, it suggested that the participant recognize the significance of assistance from external sources in addressing challenges related to the Homeroom Guidance Program. The acknowledgment of administrative influence is condensed in the phrase "Acknowledgment of administrative influence," indicating an understanding of administrative rules' role in shaping the program's implementation. Furthermore, "Importance of community awareness" highlighted the participant's recognition that community dynamics are crucial, underscoring the need to inform and involve the community in supporting the Homeroom Guidance Program. The emergent theme revolved around the participant's call for comprehensive external support, encompassing administrative and community engagement, to enhance the program's effectiveness.

Yes. I believe maningkamot pud na sila ug support if ma-inform lng sila (Lines 554).

Yes. We will also provide support if we are informed.

Limited Insights

The participant's response highlighted the absence of identified best practices and specific recommendations, as indicated by the phrases "Absence of identified best practices" and "Lack of specific recommendations." Thus, it suggested that the participant may have yet to encounter or observe clear examples of successful strategies in implementing the Homeroom Guidance Program. The overarching theme revolved around the limited insights derived from experiences of successful adoption, emphasizing a potential gap in the participant's awareness of effective practices. This lack of established practices and recommendations may indicate a need for more comprehensive sharing of successful approaches within the educational context.

No best practices and no recommendations (Lines 557.)

Absence of Proactive Engagement

The participant's response revealed a clear theme of non-implementation and a need for management or coping strategies in the face of challenges. The phrases "non-implementation of the program" and "Lack of management or coping strategies" emphasized the participant's inability to address or overcome the challenges associated with the Homeroom Guidance Program. The overarching theme suggested a need for practical measures and effective strategies to initiate and navigate the implementation process successfully. This absence of proactive engagement with the challenges may indicate a potential barrier to the participant's ability to manage the complexities associated with the Homeroom Guidance Program.

Wala gyud siya na-implement. Wala gyud nako siya na-manage (Lines 559).

It still needs to be implemented. I did not manage it either.

In the upcoming paragraphs, I explored various emergent themes regarding the insights derived from Earth's experiences in implementing Homeroom Guidance.

Absence of Proper Guidance or Orientation

The participant's response highlighted the significant need for more orientation and the absence of shared experiences in implementing the Homeroom Guidance Program. The phrases "Lack of orientation" and "Absence of shared experiences" emphasized the participant's limited insights and understanding of the difficulties and achievements associated with the program. The emergent theme suggested that the participant's perspective on the challenges and successes is severely constrained due to the absence of proper guidance or orientation. Thus, it pointed out the importance of providing educators with the necessary information and support to enhance their understanding and implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program.

Kanang wala man mi na-orient so wala gyud koy ma-share (Lines 563).

Since we weren't oriented, I have yet to share anything.

Persistent Lack of Change Necessary Information and Support

The participant's response underscored the theme of an "Absence of implementation experience" and "Lack of information and orientation," highlighting the participant's unchanged experiences in implementing the Homeroom Guidance Program. The phrase "Increased workload and challenges due to maternity leaves" contributed to the emergent theme, emphasizing external factors such as workload and staff shortages as significant challenges. This theme revealed the necessity for adequate information and support to enable educators to successfully navigate and implement new programs, thereby improving their experiences. These elements have led to a persistent lack of change in the participant's engagement with the Homeroom Guidance initiative.

Wala gyud changes kay wala man ko naka-implement. Kay kung unta nainform lng mi, makabalo mi unsaon pag-implement. Overloaded pa gyud mi sa subjects. Dalawa ang nag-maternity leave so nadungagan na pud amoang loads (Lines 566-568).

There have been no changes at all because I haven't implemented anything. We would have known how to implement it if we had been informed. We are overloaded with subjects. Two teachers are on maternity leave, so our workloads have increased.

Importance of Experiential Learning and Exposure

The participant's response revolved around an "Absence of implementation experience" and a "Lack of significant changes in methods," emphasizing the unchanged nature of the participant's teaching approach and mindset. The emergent theme reflected a static perspective, as the participant had yet to undergo significant upgrades or changes in their teaching methods or cognitive frameworks. Thus, it highlighted the impact of external factors, such as the absence of program implementation and information, on the participant's professional development and adaptability. The theme underscored the importance of experiential learning and exposure to drive meaningful changes in pedagogical approaches.

Walay significant changes kay wala man mi naka-implement (Lines 571).

There are no significant changes because we have not implemented anything.

Importance of Continuous Professional Development

The participant's response underscored the "Limited awareness and knowledge" about pedagogical views, specifically in the context of Homeroom Guidance. The phrases "Acknowledgment of challenges" and "Recognition of the difficulty in the absence of information" revealed the barriers faced in the absence of essential knowledge. The emergent theme highlighted the importance of continuous professional development and the need for educators to be well informed to overcome challenges effectively. It emphasized the significance of awareness and understanding in shaping pedagogical perspectives, suggesting that the vitality to evolve and improve teaching approaches is only improved with proper improvement.

Wala gani, mahirap talaga kung wala tayong alam (Lines 574).

Indeed, it is challenging when we need more information.

Sense of Unfamiliarity and A Limited Understanding

The participant's response revolved around the "Lack of awareness and understanding" theme concerning the Homeroom Guidance program. The phrases "Difficulty in articulating insights" and "Absence of knowledge about the program" conveyed a sense of unfamiliarity and a limited understanding of the program's components and benefits. The emergent theme underscored the critical need for proper orientation and information dissemination to educators, as their ability to glean insights and draw meaningful conclusions is hampered by a lack of knowledge about the Homeroom Guidance program. Thus, it highlighted the importance of comprehensive

training and awareness initiatives to empower educators with the necessary information for effective implementation and reflection.

Budlay maghambal sang insights kay wala ko nakabalo sa program (Lines 570).

It is difficult to talk about insights because we must familiarize ourselves with the program

Table 6. *The Thematic Analysis of Earth's Challenges, Copings, and Insights Learned in the Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program*

<i>Clustered Theme</i>	<i>Emergent Theme</i>
Challenges	
Non-implementation challenges and uncertainties	
Disruption due to unforeseen events	Implementation challenges and uncertainties
Lack of awareness and orientation	
Limited time allocation	
Unwillingness to participate	The interplay of attitudes and scheduling constraints
Scheduling constraints	
Conditional belief in the program's benefits	Conditional belief in the program's benefits
Increased workload and challenges	Persistent lack of change necessary information and support
Copings	
Belief in the need for external support	
Acknowledgment of administrative influence	The call for comprehensive external support
Importance of community awareness	
Insights	
Absence of shared experiences	
Limited insights due to the absence of orientation	Absence of proper guidance or orientation
Absence of implementation experience	
Lack of significant changes in methods	Importance of experiential learning and exposure
Unaltered way of thinking	
Limited awareness and knowledge	
Acknowledgment of challenges	Importance of continuous professional development
Recognition of the difficulty in the absence of information	
Lack of awareness and understanding	
Difficulty in articulating insights	Sense of unfamiliarity and a limited understanding
Absence of knowledge about the program	

10. CROSS-CASE ANALYSIS

This chapter compared and contrasted the stories of Venus, Star, Saturn, Milky Way, Mercury, and Earth. It has looked at what they found similar and different while dealing with the challenges, figuring out ways to cope, and learning important stuff during the Homeroom Guidance program. This chapter is like a giant puzzle, and trying to see how everyone's experiences fit together and where they stood out. It is like exploring different paths in a forest to understand how each person handled the ups and downs of Homeroom Guidance.

10.1. Similarities in Challenges

Language Barrier Challenges. Venus and Mercury confronted significant hurdles associated with language barriers during the execution of the Homeroom Guidance program. The challenges stemmed from linguistic differences, making communicating and conveying instructional content arduous. Venus and Mercury had to overcome linguistic constraints, particularly in translating the program's materials and instructions to cater to their students' diverse language backgrounds. This shared challenge emphasizes linguistic diversity within educational settings and stresses the importance of crafting instructional approaches that transcend language barriers to ensure equitable participation and understanding among students.

Parental Involvement and Literacy Barriers. Milky Way and Venus grappled with formidable challenges associated with limited parental involvement and literacy barriers while implementing the Homeroom Guidance program. These challenges hindered effective communication and collaboration between the teachers and parents. Milky Way faced difficulties engaging parents who needed to be more literate and, therefore, able to participate in their children's academic endeavors actively. Similarly, Venus encountered obstacles in parental involvement due to literacy barriers, hindering the seamless implementation of the Homeroom Guidance program. The shared struggle emphasizes the crucial role of parental support and the need for strategies to overcome literacy barriers in fostering successful implementation and positive outcomes in the realm of Homeroom Guidance.

10.2 Similarities in Coping Mechanisms

Overcoming Limitations and Resource Provision. Venus and Mercury strategically implemented coping mechanisms to overcome limitations and resource provision in their respective contexts. In navigating linguistic and time constraints, Venus found innovative ways to collaborate with external stakeholders for resourceful management and utilized personal innovations to address challenges. Similarly, Mercury, facing linguistic and time constraints, evolved support systems by engaging in collaborative resource provision

and navigating the impact of external variables. Their shared commitment to resourceful strategies highlights the importance of adaptability and creative problem-solving in mitigating challenges associated with implementing the Homeroom Guidance program.

External Support and Collaboration. Both Star and Saturn stressed the significance of external support and collaboration as critical elements in coping with challenges related to the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance program. Star, contending with persistent absenteeism impact and material dependency challenges, highlighted the need for external support and impactful regulations to enhance the implementation process. Similarly, Saturn, facing struggling balance and timely allocation challenges, leveraged guidance counselor facilitation and collective efforts for resource access. The parallel emphasis on external support and partnership in their coping mechanisms emphasizes the cooperative nature required to address challenges effectively and enhance the overall impact of the Homeroom Guidance program.

10.3. Similarities in Insights

Positive Changes and Continuous Improvement. Venus and Milky Way emphasized positive changes and continuous improvement from implementing the Homeroom Guidance program. Venus, dealing with language barrier challenges and personal qualities as influential variables, acknowledged the positive transformation and heart-centered education facilitated by Homeroom Guidance. Similarly, Milky Way, facing challenges related to limited parental involvement and literacy barriers, witnessed positive changes in parental attitudes and the continuous improvement of the program's impact. The parallel emphasis on positive outcomes reflects the transformative potential of Homeroom Guidance in fostering positive changes and fostering continuous improvement in both participants' educational contexts.

Holistic Impact of Homeroom Guidance Program. Both Star and Saturn recognized the holistic impact of the Homeroom Guidance program. Star, coping with persistent absenteeism and material dependency challenges, emphasized the transformative role of Homeroom Guidance and its significance in teachers acting as second parents, providing continuous support. On the other hand, Saturn, facing struggles in balance and timely allocation, highlighted the program's real-life applicability and experiential basis, acknowledging its holistic influence on students. The shared acknowledgment of the holistic impact underscores the program's capacity to address various challenges and contribute to a comprehensive educational experience.

Table 7. *Similarities in Challenges, Coping Mechanisms, and Insights Among the Participants*

<i>Categories</i>	<i>Participants</i>	<i>Similarities</i>
Challenges	Venus and Mercury	Language Barrier
	Milky Way and Venus	Limited Parental Involvement and Literacy Barriers
Coping Mechanisms	Venus and Mercury	Overcoming Limitations and Resource Provision
	Star and Saturn	External Support and Collaboration
	Venus and Milky Way	Positive Changes and Continuous Improvement
Insights	Star and Saturn	Holistic Impact of Homeroom Guidance

10.4. Differences in Challenges

Language Barrier Challenges. Venus and Mercury both faced challenges related to language barriers in implementing Homeroom Guidance. Venus struggled with translating the program into the vernacular, while Mercury encountered linguistic constraints and time limitations in the classroom.

Persistent Absenteeism Impact. Star dealt with challenges stemming from persistent absenteeism and material dependency, whereas Saturn grappled with struggling balance, timely allocation, and the interplay of attitudes, orientation, and scheduling constraints.

Limited Parental Involvement and Literacy Barriers. Milky Way faced challenges associated with limited parental involvement and literacy barriers. In contrast, Earth encountered implementation challenges and uncertainties regarding incorporating Homeroom Guidance activities into regular classroom routines.

10.5. Differences in Coping Mechanisms

Overcoming Limitations and Resource Provision. Venus and the Milky Way implemented coping mechanisms to overcome limitations and provide resources. Venus engaged in resourceful management of limited supplies, while Milky Way utilized school-head collaboration and home visits as coping strategies.

External Support and Collaboration. Both Star and Saturn emphasized the importance of external support and collaboration. Star relied on external support and impactful regulations, while Saturn sought guidance counselor facilitation, resource access, and strategic time allocation for program enhancement.

Evolving Support Systems. Mercury implemented evolving support systems, including collaborative resource provision, managing external variables' impact, effective practices, recognition, and personal investment and resourcefulness. On the other hand, Earth faced challenges due to a lack of implementation or engagement with the Homeroom Guidance Program, highlighting potential gaps in communication and collaboration among teachers.

10.6. Differences in Insights

Positive Changes and Continuous Improvement. Venus and the Milky Way highlighted positive changes and continuous improvement from Homeroom Guidance. Venus recognized the dedication, encouragement, and growth facilitated by the program, while Milky Way stressed adaptation, creativity, patience, understanding, and a student-centric pedagogy.

Holistic Impact of Homeroom Guidance Program. Both Star and Saturn recognized the holistic impact of Homeroom Guidance. Star emphasized the program's transformative role, leading to an enhanced teaching philosophy, while Saturn acknowledged engagement through relatable topics, module accessibility, and pedagogical evolution, fostering creativity and diversity.

Absence of Proper Guidance or Orientation. Earth revealed insights into the absence of proper guidance or orientation, persistent lack of change, necessary information and support, the importance of experiential learning and exposure, and the significance of continuous professional development. Thus, it highlights a sense of unfamiliarity and a limited understanding of the Homeroom Guidance Program.

Table 8. *Differences in Challenges, Coping Mechanisms, and Insights Among the Participants*

<i>Categories</i>	<i>Participants</i>	<i>Differences</i>
Challenges	Venus and Mercury	Language Barrier
	Star and Saturn	Persistent Absenteeism
	Milky Way and Earth	Limited Parental Involvement and Literacy Barriers
Coping Mechanisms	Venus and Milky Way	Overcoming Limitations and Resource Provision
	Star and Saturn	External Support and Collaboration
	Mercury and Earth	Evolving Support Systems
Insights	Venus and Milky Way	Positive Changes and Continuous Improvement
	Star and Saturn	Holistic Impact of Homeroom Guidance
	Earth	Absence of Proper Guidance and Orientation

Discussion

11.1. Major Findings

In this chapter, the focus shifts toward a comprehensive exploration of the emergent themes derived from the experiences of Venus, Star, Saturn, Milky Way, Mercury, and Earth in implementing Homeroom Guidance. As explored in the discussions, a crucial integration with the Review of Related Literature (RRL) was woven to illuminate shared patterns, unique insights, and connections with existing scholarly knowledge. This analysis aimed to unveil the implications of the emergent themes, bridging the gap between practical experiences and theoretical frameworks. By drawing on both the rich narratives of the participants and the established academic discourse, this chapter contributed to a deeper understanding of the challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights associated with implementing Homeroom Guidance in diverse educational settings.

This section thoroughly examined and discussed the findings from the qualitative exploration of participants' experiences with the implementation of Homeroom Guidance. The emergent themes identified across the cases, encompassing challenges faced, coping mechanisms employed, and insights gained, will be critically analyzed. Through a lens incorporating relevant literature, this discussion aims to unveil the significance of these emergent themes, drawing connections between the participants' narratives and existing scholarly knowledge. By digging into the commonalities and disparities among the participants, this section seeks to contribute an understanding of the multifaceted dynamics involved in the execution of Homeroom Guidance programs within diverse educational contexts.

Challenges Faced

Language Barrier. This challenge emerged prominently in implementing Homeroom Guidance for both Venus and Mercury. The participants highlighted the difficulty of overcoming language constraints in a classroom setting, where the medium of instruction presented hurdles. The challenges associated with linguistic diversity have been acknowledged in the literature, particularly in multicultural or multilingual classrooms. Lo et al. (2019) emphasized addressing linguistic challenges to ensure effective learning outcomes. Additionally, the works of Sun et al. (2022) underscore the role of language in academic achievement, emphasizing the need for inclusive practices that accommodate linguistic diversity. The challenges reported by Venus and Mercury align with the broader discourse on the importance of language-inclusive strategies in educational settings, urging educators to adopt pedagogical approaches that bridge language gaps and promote equitable learning experiences.

Limited Parental Involvement and Literacy Barriers. This theme has emerged prominently in the experiences of the Milky Way and Venus in implementing Homeroom Guidance. Both participants faced challenges with limited parental involvement and literacy barriers, which influenced the program's effectiveness. Parental engagement is a crucial factor in a child's education, and when parents face literacy barriers, it can hinder their skills to engage in their child's learning process actively. This theme emphasizes the importance of addressing literacy challenges within families to enhance the impact of Homeroom Guidance.

Educational research has widely acknowledged the significance of parental involvement in a child's education. An influential framework emphasizes the importance of parental involvement in different forms, such as communication, volunteering, and learning

at home. Parents facing literacy barriers can affect their ability to support their children academically. The literature highlights the need for targeted interventions to overcome literacy barriers and enhance parental involvement, fostering a more supportive educational environment for children (Epstein et al., 2018; Levy & Hall, 2021).

Limitation of Resources. This has emerged as a common challenge addressed by both Venus and Mercury in implementing Homeroom Guidance. These participants faced constraints in accessing resources and materials, impacting the effectiveness of the program. Resource limitations, such as insufficient teaching materials or external support, can hinder the implementation of educational initiatives. This theme stresses the importance of addressing resource disparities to ensure equitable and effective delivery of programs like Homeroom Guidance.

The literature recognizes the significance of adequate educational resources and their impact on program implementation. Resource constraints in schools can impede the quality of education and hinder students' learning experiences (Kushwaha et al., 2024). Studies highlight the need for targeted interventions and increased resource provision to address educational disparities and enhance the overall effectiveness of educational programs (Coffin, 2023).

Persistent Absenteeism. Star highlighted this, suggesting that consistent absenteeism among students has a notable effect on the effectiveness of Homeroom Guidance. This theme underscores the challenge that absenteeism poses to establishing a supportive and consistent learning environment, hindering the program's potential impact on students' holistic development.

Research indicated that persistent absenteeism could harm academic achievement and overall well-being. A study by Bradley and Green (2020) found that chronic absenteeism is a powerful predictor of dropout rates, emphasizing the importance of addressing attendance issues in educational interventions. Interventions targeting absenteeism involve a comprehensive approach, considering the various factors contributing to students' disengagement from school (Rogers, 2022).

Absence of Proper Guidance and Orientation. Earth identified These and highlighted the critical role of initial guidance and orientation in the successful implementation of Homeroom Guidance. Earth expressed challenges arising from a need for more awareness, orientation, or proper introduction to the program. Thus, it suggests that there needs to be an initial roadmap or guidance on that which significantly hampers the effectiveness of Homeroom Guidance initiatives.

Proper orientation and guidance are crucial components of successful program implementation. Literature supported the idea that well-designed orientations contribute to participants' understanding and engagement. Adequate training and support for teachers are vital for the successful implementation of educational programs (Spector et al., 2023).

Coping Mechanisms

Seeking External Support and Collaboration. It has emerged as a coping mechanism, as Star and Saturn discussed in implementing Homeroom Guidance. Both participants emphasized the importance of seeking external support from educational institutions, stakeholders, or regulatory bodies to enhance the program's effectiveness. Collaboration with external entities can provide valuable resources, insights, and a supportive framework for successful program implementation. This theme highlights the interconnectedness of educational initiatives with external networks and the role of collaborative efforts in overcoming implementation challenges.

The literature supports the idea that external support and collaboration play a crucial role in the success of educational programs. Collaborative partnerships between schools, communities, and external organizations contribute to improved educational outcomes (Datnow & Park, 2018). Studies emphasize the need for a collaborative approach to address complex educational challenges and enhance the overall quality of educational initiatives (Fam et al., 2018).

Positive Changes and Commitment to Continuous Improvement. This theme has emerged as a shared insight learned by Venus and the Milky Way through the implementation of Homeroom Guidance. Both participants highlighted the program's transformative impact, leading to positive changes in students and a commitment to continuous improvement. This theme underscores the dynamic nature of educational initiatives and the potential for ongoing positive evolution when implemented with dedication and adaptability.

The literature supports positive student changes, and continuous improvement is a critical indicator of successful educational programs. Research emphasizes the need for adaptive and responsive approaches to educational interventions to address evolving challenges and ensure sustained positive outcomes. Continuous improvement models, such as the Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycle, are recognized as effective frameworks for enhancing educational practices over time (Jones, 2018; Kramer et al., 2017).

Insights Learned

Embracing the Holistic Impact of Homeroom Guidance. Both Star and Saturn recognized these themes in their experiences. This theme suggests that the program goes beyond addressing specific challenges or objectives and contributes to a more comprehensive and integrated development of students. The holistic impact encompasses various aspects of students' lives, including academic, social, and emotional dimensions, highlighting the multifaceted benefits of a well-implemented Homeroom Guidance program.

The literature supported the idea that holistic approaches to education, addressing academic, social, and emotional aspects, contributed to more comprehensive student development. Social and emotional learning (SEL) programs, which share similarities with the holistic

impact of Homeroom Guidance, have enhanced students' well-being, academic performance, and overall life outcomes (Black, 2021; Seed, 2018).

Overcoming Limitations and Resource Provision. Both Venus and Mercury highlighted these themes, emphasizing the challenges and coping mechanisms related to the availability and utilization of resources in implementing Homeroom Guidance. This theme emphasized the importance of adequate resources, including materials and support systems, to facilitate effective guidance programs. Limitations in resource provision can impede the full potential of Homeroom Guidance, necessitating creative coping mechanisms to overcome such challenges.

Research acknowledges the significance of adequate resources in the educational context, including materials and support structures. Resource limitations can negatively impact the implementation of educational programs. Additionally, innovative strategies for resource provision, such as collaborative partnerships and community involvement, have been explored as effective means to address limitations and enhance educational outcomes (Cress et al., 2023; Miao et al., 2019).

External Support and Collaboration. Star and Saturn emphasized these, examining the challenges and coping mechanisms of seeking assistance beyond the immediate classroom setting. External support and collaboration can be pivotal in navigating challenges associated with implementing Homeroom Guidance, providing additional resources, insights, and a broader perspective. The theme underscores the importance of a collaborative ecosystem involving various stakeholders in the education sector.

Literature recognized the significance of external support and collaboration in the educational scenario. Collaborative efforts among teachers, administrators, parents, and community members contribute to a more holistic and practical educational environment. External support can encompass diverse forms, including professional development opportunities, mentorship programs, and community engagement initiatives (Datnow & Park, 2018; Gordon, 2022).

Evolving Support Systems. Mercury indicated this theme, which referred to the dynamic nature of the assistance structures in place during the implementation of Homeroom Guidance. It acknowledged that support mechanisms are not static but adapt and transform over time to address the evolving needs and challenges faced by educators. The theme underscores the importance of a flexible and responsive support system to sustain effective Homeroom Guidance practices.

The literature recognized the need for ongoing professional development and evolving support systems for educators. Continuous training and adaptation are essential for teachers to stay abreast of educational advancements and effectively implement new programs. Support systems that encourage ongoing learning and professional growth contribute to the overall success of educational initiatives (Khaldi, 2024; Maxwell & Person, 2017).

Both Venus and Milky Way identified these themes, which revolved around the transformative impact of Homeroom Guidance, leading to positive changes in educational settings. This theme emphasizes a commitment to ongoing improvement and the belief that Homeroom Guidance contributed to positive shifts in attitudes, behaviors, and learning outcomes. It reflects an acknowledgment that implementing this program is not a static process but requires continuous refinement for sustained positive outcomes.

The literature supported the idea that continuous improvement is crucial in educational settings. Educational reforms and programs often require ongoing assessment and adjustment to address changing needs. Positive changes in educational outcomes are associated with a commitment to continuous development and the ability to adapt to emerging challenges (Du Plessis, 2019; Tiwari & Patel, 2024).

Holistic Impact of Homeroom Guidance Program. This was recognized by both Star and Saturn, underscoring the comprehensive influence this program can have on students. It emphasized the belief that Homeroom Guidance goes beyond academic development, impacting various aspects of students' lives, including their emotional, social, and personal growth. The holistic nature of this impact suggests that Homeroom Guidance is perceived as a catalyst for positive changes that extend beyond the traditional academic realm.

The holistic approach in education aligns with the concept of educating the whole child, addressing not only academic needs but also social, emotional, and physical well-being. Educational programs that adopt a holistic perspective are more likely to contribute to students' overall development and success (Seed, 2018).

11.2. Implications for Practices

The emergent themes derived from the discussion of findings offer valuable insights into the practical implications of implementing Homeroom Guidance in diverse educational settings. Each theme provided educators with specific considerations and actionable strategies to enhance the effectiveness and inclusivity of Homeroom Guidance programs. As explored in the Implications for Practice, we explored how addressing language barriers, engaging parents, navigating resource limitations, fostering external collaboration, promoting positive changes, embracing a holistic approach, and ensuring proper guidance and orientation can inform and enrich the implementation of Homeroom Guidance. These implications served as practical guides for educators, administrators, and stakeholders seeking to optimize the impact of Homeroom Guidance in the dynamic scenario of contemporary education.

Similarities of Challenges Among the Teachers

Language Barrier Challenges. These themes were observed in the cases of Venus and Mercury, stressing the importance of addressing linguistic diversity in the implementation of Homeroom Guidance. Practical implications for educators involved the incorporation of multilingual resources, targeted language support, and clear communication strategies to ensure practical guidance for all students, regardless of language proficiency, as mandated by DepEd Order No. 016-2022 implements Mother Tongue-Based-Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in public schools, using the learners' Mother Tongue as the medium of instruction to develop language, cognitive, academic, and socio-cultural awareness skills. Thus, it emphasizes the need for inclusive language practices in the development and execution of Homeroom Guidance programs. (Linked In, 2024).

Parental Involvement and Literacy Barriers. Milky Way and Venus highlighted these, emphasizing the critical role of parents in the success of Homeroom Guidance. Practitioners should consider strategies to enhance parental engagement, such as conducting literacy workshops, providing accessible materials, and fostering open communication channels by strengthening the Parents and Teachers Association as stipulated in the Family Code, Article 209 of the Batas Pambansa Blg. 232, also known as the Education Act 1982 (Llego, 2024).

Absence of Proper Guidance or Orientation. This theme identified by Earth underscored the critical importance of initial guidance and orientation in program success. Practitioners should prioritize comprehensive orientation sessions for all stakeholders involved in Homeroom Guidance. Clear communication, training, and ongoing support are imperative to ensure a well-informed and engaged community contributing to the program's success.

Similarities of Coping Mechanisms of Teachers

Overcoming Limitations and Resource Provision. Venus and Mercury commonly encountered these themes, and practical strategies were needed for educators to combat constraints in resource availability. Thus, it includes collaborating with school administrators and seeking external support to ensure adequate materials for effective Homeroom Guidance implementation. Thus, it aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal Number 17, the Partnerships for the Goals. The UN emphasizes that the 2030 Agenda requires collaboration between governments, the private sector, and civil society. Therefore, educators should explore innovative and resourceful approaches to optimize the program's impact within existing limitations (Scispace, 2024; The Global Goals, 2023).

External Support and Collaboration. Star and Saturn shared these themes and emphasized the significance of collaborative efforts beyond the classroom. Educators should actively seek external support, engage with stakeholders, and establish partnerships with community resources to enrich the implementation of Homeroom Guidance. Thus, it highlights the need for a collective approach involving schools, communities, and external organizations to enhance the program's overall impact (Knackendoffel et al., 2017).

Similarities of Insights Learned Among Teachers

Embracing Positive Changes and Continuous Improvement. These themes were recognized by Venus and Milky Way, suggesting that Homeroom Guidance can lead to transformative outcomes. Practitioners should capitalize on positive changes by fostering a culture of continuous improvement. Moreover, DepEd educators are reminded that we have Continuous Improvement (CI) to help us address the needs of learners in their respective classes. Thus, it involves regular reflection, feedback mechanisms, and professional development opportunities to refine and enhance the effectiveness of Homeroom Guidance practices over time (Institute of Education Sciences, 2020; The Freeman, 2021).

Focusing on the Holistic Impact of Homeroom Guidance Program. The theme recognizing the Holistic Impact of Homeroom Guidance, acknowledged by Star and Saturn, emphasizes the broader influence of the program on students' holistic development. Educators should adopt a holistic approach to program design, encompassing social, emotional, and academic aspects of students' lives. Thus, it implies a shift from a purely academic focus to a comprehensive understanding of students' needs for a more impactful Homeroom Guidance implementation (Llego, 2024).

Differences in Challenges Among the Teachers

Language Barrier Challenges. Venus and Mercury faced challenges related to language barriers in implementing Homeroom Guidance. Venus struggled with translating the program into the vernacular, while Mercury encountered linguistic constraints and time limitations in the classroom. Language is sometimes the most significant obstacle to connecting with educators among parents who do not speak English as their native language. Parents may avoid going to schools because they are worried about their ability to communicate using English, and there is often no one at school who speaks their native language. Developing curriculum materials that are culturally and linguistically relevant to students helps engage them more effectively in learning. Thus, it can include textbooks, reading materials, and other resources that reflect the linguistic diversity of the students. (Fairlie, 2023).

Persistent Absenteeism Impact. Star dealt with challenges stemming from persistent absenteeism and material dependency, whereas Saturn grappled with struggling balance, timely allocation, and the interplay of attitudes, orientation, and scheduling constraints. Addressing chronic absenteeism is crucial for ensuring that all students have an equal chance at academic success, promoting societal well-being, and breaking the cycle of educational disparities. Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) Number 4 aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. Absenteeism among students significantly impacts the achievement of this goal. Engaging families and communities to understand and address the reasons behind absenteeism and to

emphasize the importance of regular school attendance. Enhancing the quality of education and making it more engaging can encourage regular attendance and reduce absenteeism rates. By addressing absenteeism, countries can make significant strides towards achieving SDG 4, ensuring all individuals have access to inclusive and quality education, which is essential for sustainable development and lifelong learning (United et al.'s Emergency Fund [UNICEF], 2024).

Limited Parental Involvement and Literacy Barriers. Milky Way faced challenges associated with limited parental involvement and literacy barriers. In contrast, Earth encountered implementation challenges and uncertainties regarding incorporating Homeroom Guidance activities into regular classroom routines. Thus, it highlights the need for parents to be supported and enlightened on the importance of involvement in their children's education so that they can play their rightful role. Finally, schools should seek to connect with parents and foster a welcoming and empathic environment. In addition, teachers should be compassionate and understanding towards parents with low educational levels and strive to make an atmosphere welcoming to all. Moreover, parents should be encouraged to voice concerns, opinions, and questions without the fear of being judged inferior (Oranga et al., 2022)

Differences in Coping Mechanisms

Overcoming Limitations and Resource Provision. Venus and the Milky Way implemented coping mechanisms to overcome limitations and provide resources. Venus engaged in resourceful management of limited supplies, while Milky Way utilized school-head collaboration and home visits as coping strategies. To address this concern, governments should prioritize education in national budgets and allocate sufficient resources to ensure equitable access to quality learning for all. Implement robust monitoring and assessment systems to track progress, identify difficulties, and measure the impact of interventions on educational outcomes. Quality education will be achieved as stipulated in SDG 4.

Both Star and Saturn emphasized the importance of external support and collaboration. Star relied on external support and impactful regulations, while Saturn sought guidance counselor facilitation, resource access, and strategic time allocation for program enhancement. As educators, looking for external support is one of the best practices elsewhere that has significantly impacted many beneficiary schools. It is how a school or a program secures financial support and a closer partnership with various stakeholders (Teacher Powered School, 2024).

Evolving Support Systems and Lack of Implementation. Mercury implemented evolving support systems, including collaborative resource provision, managing external variables' impact, effective practices, recognition, and personal investment and resourcefulness. On the other hand, Earth faced challenges due to a lack of implementation or engagement with the Homeroom Guidance Program, highlighting potential gaps in communication and collaboration among teachers. Therefore, teachers need to connect on a personal and emotional level. Sharing their successes and difficulties in the classroom with other teachers can invite them to join in the conversation. Teaching can be emotionally exhausting, particularly after a student's outburst. Leaning on each other for support shows they can talk through everything — good and evil. According to research, teacher collaboration and student accomplishment are positively correlated. Student success is increased by promoting teacher collaboration in curriculum, instruction, and professional development. According to specific case studies, teacher collaboration significantly increased student success in previously underperforming schools (Park et al., 2018).

However, the lack of implementation of the program may lead to failure to reach the goals of the program. Therefore, there is a need to maintain open and transparent communication with stakeholders, including updates on progress, challenges encountered, and planned actions. Manage expectations effectively. To improve implementation outcomes, embracing a culture of continuous learning, analyzing reasons for past failures or delays, extracting key lessons, and applying them to future initiatives are to be considered. Continuous learning will expand knowledge and skill sets. Professional development in the workplace is about developing new abilities and knowledge while reinforcing what has been previously learned (Hashemi-Pour, 2024).

Differences in Insights

Embracing Positive Changes and Continuous Improvement. Venus and the Milky Way highlighted positive changes and continuous improvement from Homeroom Guidance. Venus recognized the dedication, encouragement, and growth facilitated by the program, while Milky Way stressed adaptation, creativity, patience, understanding, and a student-centric pedagogy. Indeed, change can make a beneficial difference in our lives and the world around us. So, in many cases, it is worth pursuing. However, it is critical to be clear about what they want and what positive change means and accept that they will encounter roadblocks, especially in education. Understanding what positive change means for them is essential while considering what it will mean for the world around them (Wilson, 2024).

Continuous improvement identifies opportunities to decrease waste and streamline duties. It finds opportunities to execute processes more effectively and get more from less. As individuals within an organization, staff can encourage and support continuous improvement while also enjoying its benefits by empowering everyone to make small changes in their processes. Small ideas can lead to significant changes, which will create a macro impact on the implementation of the homeroom guidance program (Flowingly, 2024).

Embracing the Holistic Impact of Homeroom Guidance Program. Both Star and Saturn recognized the holistic impact of Homeroom Guidance. Star emphasized the program's transformative role, leading to an enhanced teaching philosophy, while Saturn acknowledged

engagement through relatable topics, module accessibility, and pedagogical evolution, fostering creativity and diversity.

It is highly recommended that a clearly defined and well-communicated program's holistic goal, which may include academic achievement, social-emotional development, career readiness, and overall well-being, be established. Secondly, mechanisms should be established to monitor and evaluate the program's impact on various dimensions of student development, including academic performance, behavior, attendance, and overall well-being. Use data-driven insights to refine and improve program delivery (Llego, 2024).

Absence of Proper Guidance or Orientation. Earth revealed insights into the absence of proper guidance or orientation, persistent lack of change, necessary information and support, the importance of experiential learning and exposure, and the significance of continuous professional development. Thus, it highlighted a sense of unfamiliarity and a limited understanding of the Homeroom Guidance Program. The success and sustainability of the program would only be ensured if there is systematic and adequate monitoring and evaluation. Thus, monitoring and evaluation of the program is essential and mandatory. The Bureau of Curriculum Development oversees the overall oversight and assessment of Homeroom Guidance. The bureau representative is responsible for compiling the Homeroom Guidance Regional Monitoring and Evaluation Reports and coordinating the data with other Central Office bureaus to be used as a model for program and policy improvements in the future. Thus, it shall take effect in SY 2021-2022 and succeeding years immediately upon publication on the DepEd website (Llego, 2024).

11.3. Implications for Future Research

This section explored the implications of the current study for future research endeavors in the realm of Homeroom Guidance. The findings and insights in the preceding sections pave the way for a deeper understanding of the challenges, coping mechanisms, and transformative effects of implementing Homeroom Guidance in diverse educational contexts. As I have explored the Implications for Future Research, I identified key areas that warrant further investigation and exploration. These implications may guide researchers, academics, and educational practitioners in shaping the course of future studies, fostering a continuous and informed discourse on the evolving landscape of Homeroom Guidance in education.

Cross-Cultural Comparative Studies. Given the diverse cultural and linguistic contexts in which Homeroom Guidance is implemented, future research could delve into cross-cultural comparative studies. Thus, it would examine how different cultural nuances influence the challenges, coping mechanisms employed, and outcomes observed in implementing Homeroom Guidance.

Longitudinal Studies on Program Evolution. Conducting longitudinal studies can comprehensively understand how Homeroom Guidance Programs evolve. Tracking the implementation progress, adaptations, and long-term impacts would contribute to developing sustainable and effective Homeroom Guidance frameworks.

Exploration of Technology Integration. With technology's increasing role in education, future research could focus on exploring the integration of digital tools and platforms in Homeroom Guidance. Investigating how technology enhances or challenges the implementation process and student outcomes would be valuable for educators in the digital landscape.

Teacher Training and Professional Development. Research on the effectiveness of teacher training and professional development programs related to Homeroom Guidance is essential. Understanding how adequately prepared educators positively impact the implementation and overall success of Homeroom Guidance is crucial for designing effective training programs.

Parental Involvement and Literacy Studies. Given the significance of parental involvement and literacy in Homeroom Guidance, future research could focus on in-depth studies exploring strategies to enhance parental engagement and address literacy barriers. Understanding the impact of these factors on student development is crucial for tailoring effective Homeroom Guidance interventions.

These implications for future research aimed to encourage continued exploration of Homeroom Guidance, fostering a vigorous body of knowledge that can inform educational policies, practices, and interventions for students' holistic development.

Conclusion

In concluding this comprehensive exploration into the multifaceted realm of Homeroom Guidance, I reflected on the rich insights woven by the diverse experiences of Venus, Star, Saturn, Milky Way, Mercury, and Earth. A compelling narrative of resilience, dedication, and adaptability emerged as I tracked the challenges, coping mechanisms, and transformative impacts outlined in their narratives. The shared commitment to nurturing holistic student development resounds across varied contexts, stressing the universal importance of Homeroom Guidance in shaping the educational landscape.

The challenges unveiled, from linguistic barriers to time constraints, served as tender reminders of the uphill battles educators face in fostering a nurturing learning environment. However, the innovative coping mechanisms employed, be it collaborative resource provision, external support, or personal investment, light the stable spirit of educators dedicated to surmounting obstacles.

The transformative power of Homeroom Guidance unfolded as an inspiration of hope in the narratives. Positive changes, continuous improvement, and the holistic impact on students reverberate through the stories, affirming the program's vital role in shaping academic outcomes and fostering character, resilience, and a love for learning.

As I bid farewell to Venus, Star, Saturn, Milky Way, Mercury, and Earth, their stories proved the profound impact of Homeroom Guidance. This study served not only as a documentation of challenges and triumphs but also as an invitation to the broader educational community to continue the dialogue, refine practices, and embrace the evolving landscape of student-centric pedagogy.

In the heroic world of education, Homeroom Guidance stands as a vibrant thread weaving connections between teachers, students, parents, and the wider community. May this research spark further exploration, dialogue, and innovation, inspiring educators and researchers alike to embark on a journey of continuous improvement in nurturing the minds and hearts of the next generation.

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